

Deliverable 1.1

Data Management Plan

2 July 2024

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*Legend = R – Report // DEM – Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs // DEC – Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc. // DMP – Data management plan // OTHER – Software, technical diagram, algorithms, models, etc.

Document History

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V1	20/06/2024	Cinzia Albanesi, Iana I. Tzankova	First draft
V2	21/06/2024	Elvira Cicognani	Minor revisions
V3	28/06/2024	Consortium members	Integrations and minor revisions
V4	02/07/2024	Cinzia Albanesi, Elvira Cicognani, Iana I. Tzankova	Minor revisions and editing

Scheduled Data Management Plan (DMP) Updates

The DMP evolves during the lifespan of the project and registers all relevant changes in the life cycle of all the research datasets. Updated versions of the DMP have already been planned (see table below). Moreover, this document will be updated whenever important changes in the data or the data management policy occur.

Table 1. DMP updates

Issue	Expected by project month (M)
Initial DMP	M6
Intermediate DMP	M30
Final DMP	M42

SINCRONY

Table 2. The SINCRONY Consortium

	Name of the Entity	Acronym	Role	Country	ORG Type
1	Alma Mater Studiorum - Università di Bologna	UNIBO	CO	IT	RTD
2	Universidade do Porto	U. PORTO	BE	PT	RTD
3	Association Européenne pour la Démocratie Locale	ALDA	BE	FR	NGO
4	WeDo Project Intelligence Made Easy SL	WeDo	BE	ES	SME
5	Aalborg Universitet	AAU	BE	DK	RTD
6	Turun Yliopisto	ATU	BE	FI	RTD
7	Universitaet Innsbruck	UIBK	BE	AT	RTD
8	Université de Genève	UNIGE	AP	CH	RTD
9	The University of Manchester	UNIMAN	AP	UK	RTD

*Legend = Role in the Project: C – Coordinator // B – Beneficiary // AP – Associated Partner // Organization Type: RTD – Research and Technological Development// PHI – Public Health Institution // Hosp – Hospital // SME – Small and medium-sized enterprises. // LC – Large Company // NGO – Non-Governmental Org.

Table 3. The SINCRONY Work Packages

	Work Packages Name	WP Leader
WP1	Coordination and Management	UNIBO
WP2	Co-Design	UNIBO
WP3	Assessment of existing practices in an intersectional lens	UTU
WP4	Power-based analysis of social narratives and experiences	UNIGE
WP5	Piloting enhancement and innovation pathways	ALDA
WP6	Evaluation	U. PORTO
WP7	Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation, and Impact	WeDo

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
AAU	Aalborg Universitet
ALDA	Association Européenne pour la Démocratie Locale
CC	Creative Commons
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DPP	Deliberative and Participatory Processes
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
I-DPP	Intersectional Deliberative and Participatory Processes
I-PARD	Intersectional Participatory Action Research-and-Deliberation
JRC	Joint Research Centre
NGO	Non-governmental Organization
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
PID	Persistent unique Identifier
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
SNS	Social Networking Sites
UIBK	Universitaet Innsbruck
UNIBO	Alma Mater Studiorum – University of Bologna
UNIGE	Universite de Geneve
UNIMAN	The University of Manchester
U.PORTO	Universidade Do Porto
UTU	Turun Yliopisto
WP	Work package

The Data Management Plan

This DMP provides details regarding all the research data collected and generated within the SINCRONY project. It explains the way research data are handled, organized, licensed and made openly available to the public, and how they will be preserved after the project is completed. The DMP also provides motivations when versions or parts of the project research data cannot be openly shared on account of third-party copyright issues, confidentiality or personal data protection requirements or when open dissemination could jeopardize the project achievements.

This DMP reflects the current state of the art of the SINCRONY project. However, the details and the final number of the project datasets may vary during the course of research. The variations will be recorded in updated versions of this DMP.

1 Data Summary

SINCRONY aims at ensuring the meaningful inclusion of youth who experience social disadvantage and marginalisation in deliberative and participatory processes (DPP). The project will target the factors and processes responsible for reproducing political inequalities in youth engagement in deliberative and participatory processes based on intergenerational and intragenerational power imbalances and youth intersectional positionalities. The goal is to offer policymakers, public servants, researchers, teachers, youth workers, facilitators of deliberative processes, and youth CSOs concrete instruments, guidelines, and solutions to renovate deliberative and participatory practices implemented in public governance and schools. The consortium of nine partners, consists of seven universities, the ALDA European network of local democracies, and WeDo a SME focusing on communication and dissemination. The project will: (a) enhance the inclusivity of deliberative practices in two local municipalities (in Italy and Finland); (b) design, test, and deliver an innovative, co-constructed intersectional approach called the Intersectional Participatory Action Research-and-Deliberation, piloted in seven local municipalities and four schools (in Italy, Portugal, the UK, and Denmark); (c) design participatory formats; (d) create tools; (e) define ethical guidelines. By improving the democratic quality, inclusiveness, effectiveness, and legitimacy of deliberative and participatory processes, the project will contribute to greater social justice for all youth.

To achieve those ambitious aims the project is organized in 7 WPs: One focuses on Management (WP1) one on Dissemination/Exploitation (WP7); two WPs are entirely devoted to research (WP3 and WP4) while WP5 and WP6 are dedicated to pilot implementation (WP5) and evaluation (WP6). WP2 provides an integrative framework of Theoretical and Empirical Knowledge collected and developed through the project. Research WPs will allow to collect data on a) factors related to systemic exclusion and reproduction of intergenerational and intragenerational power imbalances based on intersectional positionality b) processes of meaning-making, acceptance, or

contestation of corrosive narratives on participation; c) needs and opportunities for innovative practices by and for youth in claiming participative space and countering power relations in relevant proximal contexts (schools, communities) and governance.

Through a multi-method approach, the consortium will analyse top-down discourses (relevant EU policies and 30 national/regional policy documents (task 4.1.1) and of 8 EU and national policymakers (task 4.1.2); and bottom-up discourses – of young people in schools and organisations/activist groups (at least 20 organisations' social media (task 4.2.1.), 80 young people involved in focus groups (task 4.2.3), and 2500 – in a survey (task 4.2.2). The consortium will also analyse EU level deliberative and participatory practices (task 3.2), and deliberative and participatory practices implemented at the national and local level (task 3.3).

The project will use and generate data from the following public data sources: public databases (e.g., Participedia, Politicize, OECD), documentary sources that can be asked to/provided by the consortium stakeholders boards, available through European, National and local Centres/organisations with a focus on DPP (e.g., JRC Competence Centre on Participatory and Deliberative Democracy; Regional or Local councillorship for participation) as part of task 3.2 and 3.3. of WP3. Public databases will also be used to collect policy documents that will be analysed as part of the task 4.1.1. of WP4, which is devoted to policy document analysis.

Other sources of existing data to be used are posts in social networks: in particular, we will analyse the narratives conveyed by policymakers and institutions (task 4.2.1, WP4) that can have a particular influence in shaping opportunities for youth inclusion, diversity, recognition, and participation. Social media content/narratives produced by young people belonging to specific organisations will also be analysed (task 4.2.3., WP4).

Despite the fact that the aforementioned data are derived from public sources, the way they are put together and organized is unique to the project. Even if there are public databases that collect and organize participatory practices (e.g. Participedia), there is no existing database considering the intersectional dimension of deliberative and participatory practices nor at the EU level nor at the national level (at least in the countries of consortium members). Regarding SNS, similar considerations can apply: the information that we will collect and analyse on SNS are in the public domain, but their selection is guided by a specific analytic approach that requires that they are treated as generated dataset. As such the dataset referring to the aforementioned data/task can be considered generated, even if they are available from public sources.

Data explicitly produced within SINCRONY (e.g. totally generated as part of the research and intervention developed thanks to the project) will be generated using qualitative and quantitative methodologies. Surveys and focus groups will be used for the following WP4 tasks: Task 4.2.2 Survey of youth experience of intersectional

exclusion and inclusion and Task 4.2.3 Focus groups with adolescents and young people. While longitudinal (pre-post) surveys and interviews, as well as field observations are planned to be used for the evaluation of the pilot implementation as part of the WP6 tasks: Task 6.1 Process and qualitative evaluation, Task 6.2 Pre-post quantitative outcome evaluation, Task 6.3 Policy and community impact evaluation

In particular:

- Cross national survey
- Focus group
- Longitudinal (pre-post) survey
- Interviews
- Field observation

To sum up SINCRONY will produce different types of data by using different methodologies:

- Collections of content analysis grids used for qualitative and quantitative analysis of publicly available documentary sources (policy documents, documents of practices of participation and deliberation) [textual data, textual tabular data];
- Collections of content analysis grids used qualitative and quantitative analysis of SNS accessible in the public domain (Instagram accounts of policy makers/political parties/youth organizations) [textual data, textual tabular data];
- Focus groups (transcripts of discussions conducted in schools, youth organizations, with pilot participants' as part of the evaluation of pilot implementations) [textual qualitative data];
- Cross-national cross-sectional survey (spreadsheet of quantitative anonymized data) [statistical data];
- Cross-national longitudinal survey (spreadsheet of quantitative anonymized data to assess pilot implementation) [statistical data]
- Interviews (transcripts of interviews conducted for the evaluation of pilot implementations), [textual qualitative data];
- Field observations (transcripts of field notes of team members involved in the evaluation of pilot implementations) [textual qualitative data, visual data]

Research teams have agreed to convert research data from proprietary formats to well-known and documented open formats in order to facilitate accessibility and reusability (Table 4).

Table 4. Summary of data formats

Type of data	Formats used during data processing	Formats for sharing, reuse and preservation
Numerical or textual tabular data (e.g. analytical grids)	Microsoft Excel (.xls/.xlsx)	Comma-separated values (.csv), Tab-delimited Unicode text (.txt), OpenDocument Spreadsheet (.ods), Microsoft Excel (.xls/.xlsx, especially in case of conversion problems)
Statistical data (survey)	SPSS format (.sav)	SPSS format (.sav, .dat, .sps), SPSS portable format (.por); Comma-separated values (.csv), Microsoft Excel (.xls/.xlsx, especially in case of conversion problems)
Textual data	Microsoft Word (.doc/.docx)	Unicode text (.txt), OpenDocument text (.odt), Microsoft Word (.doc/.docx, especially in case of conversion problems)
Audio data	mp3	Audio recordings of the focus group and interviews will be destroyed after transcriptions for ethical reasons.

Read me files explaining all relevant details regarding data collection, processing methodologies and quality assurance are deposited along with the datasets in *.odt*, *.rtf* or *.pdf* format.

The overall size of the openly shareable data is around 5.0 GB. Considering the early stage of the project, the effective size may vary with respect to what is declared in the present document. Potential variations will be addressed in further versions of this document.

The data produced can be of interest to different potential users inside and outside the project.

Data produced as part of WP3 are of interest to understand what practices and experiences related to youth participation and deliberation can be found across our countries of study and to what extent intersectional inclusion is considered in these practices, and how. This is a key understanding of the project, that is of interest both to researchers of the consortium, but also to researchers outside the consortium, who are interested in participatory and deliberative practices (e.g. political scientists) and empirical research on intersectionality (e.g. sociologists). They can be interested in comparative research, in the methodologies that have been adopted to selected and evaluated practice with an intersectional lens. Youth and community organizations, as well as municipalities, public servants and policy makers can be interested in the evaluative dimension of the research, that may allow them to understand to what

extent different practices are recognised to address intersectionality, inclusion, participation, etc.

Data produced as part of WP4, taken as a whole, will be of interest to understand the inter- and intra-generational narratives and power relations in deliberative and participative democracy – how youth are represented and how they represent themselves in terms of agency and intersectional structures of oppression. This is critical knowledge that the project will develop which is of primary importance for consortium members (as it will be used to offer suggestions to make more inclusive participatory and deliberative practices for any youth) but may be of interest to youth organizations, policymakers, youth workers, municipalities to understand young people perspectives, their actions and reactions toward the different narratives that can be developed by different political actors.

Data produced as part of WP6 are of interest to understand how to assess (innovative) practices of participation and deliberation using qualitative and quantitative methods. Data is of interest both to researchers of the consortium, but also to researchers outside the consortium who may be interested in the approach adopted for evaluation, its sensitivity, its capacity to assess effectively the processes and the outcomes. Public servants, community organizations, and youth leaders may be interested in the evaluation tools developed by the project.

2 FAIR Data

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

To improve findability of research data produced during the SINCRONY project, datasets will be deposited in trusted¹ data repositories if and when appropriate. During the course of the project, and at least at the moment of publication of project results, each research team will deposit and describe the relative underlying datasets. Trusted data repositories can attribute persistent unique identifiers (PIDs) to the deposited items.

In particular, the repositories identified by the consortium, which are summarized in Table 2, attribute DOIs. Persistent Identifiers allow the citation of datasets within the related research publications.

Moreover, the chosen data repositories support standard descriptive metadata to ensure datasets indexing and discoverability. The data sets will be described using standard metadata such as Dublin Core and DataCite Metadata Schema. In particular, they adopt OAI-PMH interoperability protocol, Dublin Core and DataCite Metadata Schema and comply with the OpenAIRE 4.0 requirements for data archives. As a

¹ Search your field repository in <https://www.re3data.org/>

consequence, the project data sets will be visible through the OpenAIRE portal, facilitating the retrieval of the project results.

Documentation will be provided for the dataset, alongside the data themselves. A 'readme' file will explain the structure and use of the dataset, providing information regarding data set authorship, terms of reuse and responsibilities, explaining data set content and structure, collection procedures and analysis (such as file specifics, methodologies, codebooks of variables, data sources, and further necessary notes)

Specific keywords derived, when possible, from thesauri and controlled vocabularies will be associated to each dataset to enhance semantic discoverability.

SINCRONY research data are organized in datasets, which are named collections of data units with the same focus and scope. In this DMP are suggested the following common rules for dataset naming in order to improve data visibility, discoverability, citation and permanent online tracking.

The recommended dataset title structure consists of:

PROJECT ACRONYM, Work Package Number, TaskNumber, Brief description of dataset content, version number

Example:

SINCRONY WP3 TASK 3.2 Assessment of Deliberative and Participatory Practices with Youth in the EU V1

The version number of the dataset will be added at the end of the title in case of data revisions to help identifying the dataset updates (see *Annex I* for dataset names, unique identifiers and descriptions).

The DMP recommends also the following rules for file naming:

- for dataset file(s)

PROJECT ACRONYM_Work Package Number_Task Number_Brief description of file content_Date(YYYYMMDD)_Version Number.file extension

Example:

SINCRONY_WP3_TASK3.2_Assessment of Deliberative and Participatory Practices with Youth in the EU (20240930)_V1.csv

- for readme file(s)²
PROJECT ACRONYM_Work Package Number_Task Number_ Brief description of file content_Date (YYYYMMDD)_Version Number_README.file extention

Example:

SINCRONY_WP3_TASK3.2_Assessment of Deliberative and Participatory Practices with Youth in the EU (20240930)_V1_Readme.rtf

2.2 Making data openly accessible

As a guiding principle, SINCRONY seeks to make all research data openly available as soon as possible and ensure open access — via the repository — in order to allow dissemination, validation and re-use of research results.

To this purpose, all possible and legitimate actions and strategies are adopted to allow data sharing including:

- converting the files to standard open formats;
- providing all relevant documentation and explanation for the data and the datasets;
- obtaining copyright permissions from third party data owners to be allowed to re-use, reproduce and distribute the collected data;
- anonymizing and aggregating the data;
- in case of copyright on raw data derived, collected or elaborated from pre-existing databases or from other original sources (i.e. papers, journal articles, book chapters, reports, video and audio sources), collected data will be made available if the reproduction and sharing are allowed by expressed permission of the right holders or by applicable copyright exceptions and exemptions. Otherwise, only aggregate data resulting from the analysis will be openly published. When the sources are freely available on-line in their original repositories, but direct reproduction is not allowed, a detailed account on how the dataset was created from the original data will be provided, together with the specification of open repositories from where the original datasets are available. Raw data consisting in full texts will not be made available without the copyright holders' permission.

Restrictions to access are applied only in the following cases:

- collected data belong to third party which have denied permission for sharing on account of confidentiality and proprietary issues;
- data anonymization is not possible;

² A “README” file is a document containing relevant information about dataset authorship, terms of reuse and responsibilities, explaining dataset content and structure, collection procedures and analysis (such as file specifics, methodologies, codebooks of variables, data sources, and further necessary notes). (See Annex III to visualize the suggested README file template).

- data availability would jeopardize the project's main aim.

For data that fall under some of the restrictions described above and for which it is not possible to take any action to make them shareable, EU allows complete closure or restricted access to them. In SINCRONY access will not be open for focus group transcripts, even if they will be anonymized, because they will involve minors (see section 9); as well as for data on existing national and local practices of participation and deliberation in order to protect anonymity and prevent potential reputational harm to the evaluated organizations and schools.

See Annex I for details on the accessibility of each dataset. In most cases, when deposit in a secure repository is possible, metadata will be made openly available and licenced under a “No Rights Reserved” CC0 license or equivalent, as per the Grant Agreement, and will contain information on how to access the data.

The chosen data repositories for non-sensitive and shareable data of the project guarantee long term preservation and attribute persistent unique identifiers to the archived datasets. They support open licenses and different access levels. Moreover, they comply with the OpenAIRE 4.0³ requirements for data archives. As a consequence, the project datasets will be visible via the OpenAIRE portal, facilitating project reporting procedures. Finally, they adopt descriptive metadata standards such as Dublin Core and DataCite Metadata Schema, as required by the OpenAIRE guidelines, and allow cross-linking between publications and the relevant datasets. Please see the table below for more detail.

Each different dataset is deposited by the team that is responsible for the data collection and management in the repository of their choice. Please see the table below for more detail.

Table 5. Summary of repositories

Partner	Repository name	Type	URL	PID	OpenAIRE compatibility
UNIBO	AMS Acta	Institutional	https://amsacta.unibo.it/	DOI	Yes
U. PORTO	Zenodo	Multidisciplinary	https://zenodo.org/	DOI	Yes
AAU	Zenodo & AAU Datadeposit	Multidisciplinary & Institutional	https://zenodo.org/ & https://www.en.its.aau.dk/claudia/datadeposit	DOI	Yes
UTU	Zenodo	Multidisciplinary	https://zenodo.org/	DOI	Yes
UNIGE	Zenodo & FORS Center	Multidisciplinary & Institutional	https://zenodo.org/ & https://forscenter.ch/data-services/ch	DOI	Yes
UNIMAN	Figshare	Multidisciplinary	https://figshare.com/	DOI	Yes

³ OpenAIRE, <https://guidelines.openaire.eu/en/latest/>

2.3 Making data interoperable

All deposited datasets will be described using standard descriptive metadata, like Dublin Core and DataCite Metadata Schema in order to ensure metadata interoperability for indexing and discoverability. All relevant documentation explaining codebooks, users' manuals, data collection procedures and analysis will be made available along with the data in order to guarantee intelligibility, reproducibility and the validation of the project findings.

To allow data exchange and re-use among researchers, institutions, organisations, countries, etc., partners will convert all shareable data from proprietary formats and will make them available in well-known and documented open formats (see Table 4 for details), as much as possible compliant with available (open) software applications.

In case a particular software is used in data processing, full explanation and instructions will be included in the deposited documentation (a summary of the tools and software necessary to reuse of datasets is described in Table 6).

Table 6. Summary of tools and software for enabling re-use of the datasets

Tools/software
Open spreadsheet and document editors, such as OpenOffice ⁴ or LibreOffice ⁵
Free CSV file viewers, such as CSV viewer ⁶
R , free software environment for statistical computing and graphics
Jamovi, open statistical software for the desktop and cloud

Data produced are related to specific WPs - TASKs which will be referenced within the dataset. Data produced will be used for scientific publications (scientific papers, books, chapters, etc.), but also for informative activities, guidelines, and educational tools to be used by scholars, public servants, youth workers, school authorities and teachers.

2.4 Increase data re-use

SINCRONY distributes the shareable data by adopting licenses that allow re-use of the data and of the datasets in their entirety by other scholars and stakeholders after the end of the project. The datasets are made available under CC BY 4.0 license, unless there are constraint that require a more restrictive license (see section 2.2). Readme files with information on methodology, participants codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement will be provided for each dataset,

⁴ OpenOffice: <http://www.openoffice.org/>

⁵ LibreOffice: <https://www.libreoffice.org/>

⁶ <https://csvviewer.com/>

in order to make data usable by third parties. The provenance of the data will be thoroughly documented using the standard described in section 2.3.

It is possible that an embargo period may be applied to some datasets to allow full exploitation of research results by the team. At the moment this has not been planned yet. Any embargoes to be applied to the datasets will be specified in later versions of this DMP.

Concerning data quality assurance processes SINCRONY has sought to standardize data collection and production by adopting common guidelines that guarantee uniformity, comparability and reproducibility of the research data. WP leaders, task leaders and team leaders will take measures to ensure data accuracy and quality by providing common data collection grids, training and supervising data collectors and researchers, monitoring and cross-checking data processing and analysis.

Specifically, concerning:

Task 3.2 Mapping and analysing EU-level DPP: the task leaders will take measures to ensure data accuracy, quality, and consistency. Data entry will be monitored to ensure that data conforms to expected formats. Backup versions are regularly saved during the analysis, enabling rollback to previous versions if corruption or data loss occurs.

Task 3.3 Mapping and analysing community and local level practices: the task coordinator set the inclusion/exclusion criteria for the selection of initiatives/projects. Criteria compliance and the quality of the analysis will be enforced by the task coordinator by revising preliminary versions of the analytical grid. The final data set will only include data approved by the task coordinator.

Task 4.1.1 Analysis of social narratives on youth inclusion and participation in policies and among policymaker: the task leader will take measures to ensure data accuracy and quality by providing clear instruction for data collection, cross checking data collection grids, translation and translation. The task leader team will monitor data collection procedure, data processing and analysis.

Task 4.1.2 Policy-makers narratives: social media analysis of how youth are represented by authorities/policymakers: The task coordinator will identify criteria for the selection of relevant institutional authorities, policymakers and decision-makers at the EU, national, and local levels. A time frame and a target number of posts will also be identified by the coordinator. Specific guidelines for the visual and textual analysis (e.g., discourse analysis, visual frame analysis, conversational analysis) of the data collected by each national team will also be provided.

Task 4.2.2 Survey of youth experience of intersectional exclusion and inclusion and Task 6.2 Pre-post quantitative outcome evaluation: the task coordinator have taken measures to ensure data accuracy and quality by providing clear instruction for data

collection, cross checking data collection grids, translation and translation and correspondence between translated versions on Qualtrics platform. The task coordinator team will be in charge of monitoring data collection procedure, of data processing and analysis.

Task 4.2.3 Focus group discussions with adolescents and young people: the task leader will take measures to ensure data accuracy and quality by providing clear instruction for data collection, cross checking data collection grids, translation. The task leader team will be in charge of monitoring data collection procedure, of data processing and analysis.

Task 6.1: Interviews and focus groups with participants in the intervention: The research team coordinating this task will provide other partners with clear guidelines and workshops for data management and for conducting and analysing the interviews and focus group discussions. The coordination team will also provide feedback on each national report using this data.

Task 6.3: Interviews with policymakers: The research teams coordinating this task will provide other partners with clear guidelines for data management and for conducting and analysing the interviews. The coordination teams will also provide feedback on each national report using this data.

Metadata of shareable deposited data will be open available under a Creative Commons “No Rights Reserved” (CC0) license or equivalent.

Besides their deposition in trusted repositories, which will grant their re-usability by third parties after the end of the project, deposited data are given full citation from official project publications and web sites.

As stated in section 2.2. focus group transcript with minors (that will be collect as part of task 4.2.3) will not be openly available , in order to comply with ethical requirements of the task leader (University of Manchester) ethic board and to minimize risks of discrimination and stigmatisation given that the research activity involves experiences of and narratives on intersectional youth who experience multiple forms of marginalization such as gender identity, race, sexual orientation and class. Moreover, data on existing national and local practices of participation and deliberation (Task 3.3.) will also not be openly available in order to protect anonymity and prevent potential reputational harm to the evaluated organizations and schools.

3 Other research outputs

The SINCRONY project will develop additional research outputs in particular:

- The Inclusivity footprint calculator (an interactive web-based database with an inclusivity calculator)
- Social portraits online card game (toolkits for I-PARD training and implementation)
- Toolkits for I-DPP/ I-PARD training and implementation
- Toolbox with evaluation instruments and results for I-DPP/ I-PARD

Details about additional data management strategies with regard to the aforementioned research outputs will be included in the final version of the DMP.

4 Allocation of resources

Making data FAIR requires an investment of money and researchers' time.

Task leaders generating or reusing research data are responsible for their quality, organisation, management, and secure storage during research and for their deposit for publication and preservation according to the instructions provided in the project Data Management Plan. The activities related to the DMP (such as providing guidance on data management and open access issues and preparing the DMP) will cost about 1 person/month per year per partner for the whole duration of the project. No costs are expected for the deposit and preservation of research outputs as the chosen repositories do not apply fees.

Responsible for data management are the datasets creators (see Table 7). Researchers are encouraged to identify themselves with the unique persistent identifier ORCID⁷.

Table 7. Summary and contacts of the Dataset Creators

Team	Dataset Creator	ORCID ID	Mail
UNIBO	Cinzia Albanesi	0000-0001-8240-6159	cinzia.albanesi@unibo.it
U. PORTO	Filipe Piedade	0000-0001-6490-5472	fpiedade@fpce.up.pt
AAU	Maria Bruselius-Jensen	0000-0002-4322-8254	mariabj@ikl.aau.dk
UTU	Miikka Korventausta	0000-0002-2873-3463	miikka.korventausta@utu.fi
UNIGE	Marco Giugni	0000-0001-7210-339X	marco.giugni@unige.ch
UNIMAN	Hilary Pilkington	0000-0002-4041-430X	hilary.pilkington@manchester.ac.uk

Moreover, partners are encouraged to identify and cite all contributors (See Table 8) participating in data management activities, specifying their roles according to a given standard vocabulary (DataCite Metadata Schema).

⁷ Registration is free of charge for researchers and allows for automated linkages between the researched identity and his research activities and outputs. <https://orcid.org/>

Table 8. Summary of the team members involved in the datasets collection and management

Team	Member	ORCID ID	Role
UNIBO	Elvira CICOGNANI	0000-0002-8653-290X	<i>Project Member</i>
	Cinzia Albanesi	0000-0001-8240-6159	<i>Project Member</i>
	Gabriele Prati	0000-0002-0749-183X	<i>Project Member</i>
	Iana Ivanova Tzankova	0000-0001-7172-2009	<i>Project Member</i>
	Christian Compare	0000-0003-4360-9257	<i>Researcher</i>
	Antonella Guarino	0000-0003-3742-5574	<i>Researcher</i>
	Maric Martin Lorusso		<i>Researcher</i>
	Annalisa Cecconi		<i>Researcher</i>
U.PORTO	Isabel Menezes	0000-0001-9063-3773	<i>Project Member</i>
	Sofia Marques da Silva	0000-0002-2688-1171	<i>Project Member</i>
	Sofia Castanheira Pais	0000-0003-2841-9922	<i>Project Member</i>
	Pedro Ferreira	0000-0002-5010-7397	<i>Project Member</i>
	Norberto Ribeiro	0000-0001-7581-7902	<i>Project Member</i>
	Ana Costa	0000-0001-6611-5298	<i>Project Member</i>
	Filipe Piedade	0000-0001-6490-5472	<i>Researcher</i>
AAU	Maria Bruselius-Jensen	0000-0002-4322-8254	<i>Project Member</i>
	Louise Dånge	0000-0002-3965-2001	<i>Researcher</i>
	Lika Hansen da Cruz		<i>Researcher</i>
	Helene Hoffmann Jensen		<i>Researcher</i>
UTU	Maija Setälä	0000-0002-9341-5584	<i>Project Member</i>
	Miikka Korventausta	0000-0002-2873-3463	<i>Researcher</i>
	Janette Huttunen	0000-0003-0683-9344	<i>Researcher</i>
	Mikko Leino	0000-0002-8113-7732	<i>Researcher</i>
	Victor Sanchez-Mazas		<i>Researcher</i>
UNIGE	Marco Giugni	0000-0001-7210-339X	<i>Project Member</i>
	Valentina Holecz	0000-0002-8090-1815	<i>Researcher</i>
	Nenad Stojanovic	0000-0002-3973-6045	<i>Researcher</i>
	Victor Sanchez-Mazas		<i>Researcher</i>
UNIMAN	Hilary Pilkington	0000-0002-4041-430X	<i>Project Member</i>
	Nadim Mirshak	0000-0002-6493-5361	<i>Researcher</i>

Keys for “Role” column: *Data Collector* (such as survey conductors, interviewers...), *Producer* (person responsible for the form of a media product), *Project Member* (a researcher indicated in the GA), *Researcher* (an assistant to one of the authors who helped with research, data collection, processing and analysis but is not part of team indicated in the GA), *Research Group* (the name of a research institution or group that contributed to the dataset).

See *Annex I* for details about data management responsibilities related to each project dataset.

5 Data security

Before publication, files containing questionnaire data for statistical analysis, transcripts of interviews and focus groups, transcripts of field observations, photos, minutes, videos, action diaries etc. will be stored in computers, laptops, intranets or hard drives of the research institutions accessible through institutional password modified periodically (every 3 months in case of storage of sensitive data) and protected by regularly updated antiviruses. All the research materials stored in computers are subjected to regular back-ups (according to each institutions' regulations) in order to safeguard them from accidental losses.

The data that cannot be made accessible openly on account of copyright and privacy issues are held in secure local systems with password and regular back-ups at each involved partner institution. They will be preserved for at least five years after the project is completed.

Long term preservation and security of public data is ensured by the chosen public or institutional data repositories that are trustworthy and have specific preservation and security policies.

6 Ethics

Formal approval from the Ethics Committee of each university involved in the data collection has been required. UTU will not seek formal approval, since the research activities do not involve minors under the age of 15 or other elements requiring ethical review according to the Finnish National Board on research integrity TENK guidelines (TENK 2019). The processing of personal data, including the special categories of personal data (pursuant to art. 9 GDPR) and the secondary use of personal data, will be carried out only for the specific purposes of the project and according to the correct legal bases. In compliance with the principle of minimization, only the personal data necessary for the pursuit of the indicated research purposes will be collected during the project and will be kept for the time necessary to achieve them, as will be specified to the participants in data collection. Regarding focus group with minors, the consortium decided not to share transcripts. The research activity involves experiences of and narratives on intersectional youth who experience multiple forms of marginalization such as gender identity, race, sexual orientation and class. This might place focus group participants vulnerable to discrimination and stigmatisation. For this ethical reason, all data will be pseudonymized, and the raw data will not be openly accessible. For ethical reasons the participants will not be singled out as minority youth when recruited. The consortium also decided to protect data on existing national and local practices of participation and deliberation, even though it is based on publicly available documents, since no prior permission is asked from organizations and schools to assess their activities and the assessment may expose them to risks of reputational harm or jeopardize the anonymity of members/staff.

Annex I: Datasets descriptions

The analytic descriptions of the expected datasets of SINCRONY project are reported in this Annex organized by work-packages.

WP3 ASSESSMENT OF EXISTING PRACTICES IN AN INTERSECTIONAL LENS

WP3: WP3 analyses through an intersectional lens existing practices and experiences related to youth participation and deliberation on an EU level (Task 3.2), as well as on a national/local level in Denmark, Finland, Italy, Portugal, and the UK (Task 3.3). The data help understand whether and how intersectional inclusion is considered in existing practices, the extent to which marginalised and excluded youth are recognised and involved, what are the strengths and limitations for challenging systematic exclusion and power imbalances in participation and deliberation.

Lead: UTU

Participants: UNIMAN, AAU, ALDA, UIBK, UNIBO, UNIGE, U.PORTO

Months: 4-16

Potential users for the datasets of this WP include researchers outside the consortium, who are interested in participatory and deliberative practices (e.g. political scientists) and empirical research on intersectionality (e.g. sociologists). They can be interested in comparative research, in the methodologies that have been adopted to selected and evaluated practice with an intersectional lens. Youth and community organizations, as well as municipalities, public servants and policy makers can be interested in the evaluative dimension of the research, that may allow them to understand to what extent different practices are recognised to address intersectionality, inclusion etc.

1	in progress	<i>SINCRONY WP3 T3.2 Assessment of Deliberative and Participatory Practices with Youth in the EU V1</i>
ID [ID type]		Not yet available [DOI]
Chosen repository		Zenodo, https://zenodo.org
Version		1.0
Team in charge		UTU
Creator/s		Korventausta, Miikka [UTU]
Contributor/s		Huttunen, Janette [UTU]; Setälä, Maija [UTU]; Leino, Mikko [UTU];
Contact Person/s		Korventausta, Miikka [UTU], miikka.korventausta@utu.fi ;

1	in progress	<i>SINCRONY WP3 T3.2 Assessment of Deliberative and Participatory Practices with Youth in the EU V1</i>
Contents		The dataset consists of descriptive data and evaluation data. The descriptive data considers EU-level deliberative and participatory practices, e.g. name of the project, type of the project, and its relationship to youth. The evaluation data is manually generated from documents that are manually collected from public repositories and websites. Each of the projects is analysed through an evaluation framework, which forms the evaluation data. The evaluation framework includes various dimensions which are used to analyse the projects, e.g. external inclusion, internal inclusion, purpose, and outcomes. The data can be reused by researchers who want to compare our data with similar data collected at other points in historical time as well as in other geographical areas.
Data format		MS Excel (.xlsx), non-proprietary numerical tabular or comma-separated data (.txt, .csv)
Data volume		5 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB
Accessibility		Open access (CC BY 4.0)
Related publication/s		Not yet available

2	in progress	<i>SINCRONY WP3 T3.3 Assessment of Deliberative and Participatory Practices with Youth in Denmark V1</i>
ID [ID type]		Not yet available
Chosen repository		DataDeposit, Aalborg University (controlled access repository)
Version		1.0
Team in charge		AAU
Creator/s		Bruselius-Jensen, Maria [AAU];
Contributor/s		Hansen da Cruz, Lika [AAU]; Dånge, Louise [AAU], Helene Hoffmann, Jensen [AAU]
Contact Person/s		Dånge, Louise [AAU], louseba@ikl.aau.dk;
Contents		<p>This data includes analytical description templates based on publicly available documents that led to the identification of 5 school and 10 community initiatives/projects recognized as good practices of deliberation/participation in Denmark. The data contribute to evaluating existing Danish deliberative and participatory practices. Qualitative data, based on thematic analysis, is generated in this task in order to understand:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What practices and experiences related to youth participation and deliberation are to be found across our countries of study 2. a) To what extent intersectional inclusion is considered in these practices, and how b) To what extent marginalised and excluded youth are recognised and involved in these practices?

2	in progress	<i>SINCRONY WP3 T3.3 Assessment of Deliberative and Participatory Practices with Youth in Denmark V1</i>
		3. The strengths and limitations for challenging systematic exclusion and power imbalances through youth participation and deliberation Access to the data will be restricted in order to protect anonymity and prevent potential reputational harm related to the critical assessment of specific organisations and schools. Anonymized excerpts will be published via D3.2 “Assessment of national and local practices”.
Data format		MS Word (.docx), non-proprietary Unicode text format (.txt, .odt)
Data volume		5 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB
Accessibility		Excerpts: Open access (CC BY 4.0) Full data: Restricted access
Related publication/s		Not yet available

3	in progress	<i>SINCRONY WP3 T3.3 Assessment of Deliberative and Participatory Practices with Youth in Italy V1</i>
ID [ID type]		Not yet available [DOI]
Chosen repository		AMSActa, institutional repository of Alma Mater Studiorum – University of Bologna, https://amsacta.unibo.it
Version		1.0
Team in charge		UNIBO
Creator/s		Albanesi, Cinzia [UNIBO]
Contributor/s		Cicognani, Elvira [UNIBO]; Prati, Gabriele [UNIBO]; Tzankova, Iana I. [UNIBO]; Compare, Christian [UNIBO]; Guarino, Antonella [UNIBO]
Contact Person/s		Albanesi, Cinzia [UNIBO], cinzia.albanesi@unibo.it ;
Contents		<p>This data includes analytical description templates based on publicly available documents that led to the identification of 5 school and 10 community initiatives/projects recognized as good practices of deliberation/participation in Italy. The data contribute to evaluating existing Italian deliberative and participatory practices. Qualitative data, based on thematic analysis, is generated in this task in order to understand:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What practices and experiences related to youth participation and deliberation are to be found across our countries of study 2. a) To what extent intersectional inclusion is considered in these practices, and how b) To what extent marginalised and excluded youth are recognised and involved in these practices? 3. The strengths and limitations for challenging systematic exclusion and power imbalances through youth participation and deliberation <p>Access to the data will be restricted in order to protect anonymity and prevent potential reputational harm related to the critical assessment</p>

3	in progress	<i>SINCRONY WP3 T3.3 Assessment of Deliberative and Participatory Practices with Youth in Italy V1</i>
		of specific organisations and schools. Anonymized excerpts will be published via D3.2 “Assessment of national and local practices”.
Data format		MS Word (.docx), non-proprietary Unicode text format (.txt, .odt)
Data volume		5 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB
Accessibility		Excerpts: Open access (CC BY 4.0) Full data: Restricted access
Related publication/s		Not yet available

4	in progress	<i>SINCRONY WP3 T3.3 Assessment of Deliberative and Participatory Practices with Youth in the UK V1</i>
ID [ID type]		Not yet available
Chosen repository		Closed access repository
Version		1.0
Team in charge		UNIMAN
Creator/s		Pilkington, Hilary [UNIMAN];
Contributor/s		Mirshak, Nadim [UNIMAN];
Contact Person/s		Pilkington, Hilary [UNIMAN], hilary.pilkington@manchester.ac.uk;
Contents		<p>This data set includes analytical description templates based on publicly available documents that led to the identification of 5 school and 10 community initiatives/projects recognized as good practices of deliberation/participation in the UK. The data contribute to evaluating existing UK deliberative and participatory practices.</p> <p>Qualitative data, based on thematic analysis, is generated in this task in order to understand:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What practices and experiences related to youth participation and deliberation are to be found across our countries of study 2. a) To what extent intersectional inclusion is considered in these practices, and how b) To what extent marginalised and excluded youth are recognised and involved in these practices? 3. The strengths and limitations for challenging systematic exclusion and power imbalances through youth participation and deliberation <p>Access to the data will be restricted in order to protect anonymity and prevent potential reputational harm related to the critical assessment of specific organisations and schools. Anonymized excerpts will be published via D3.2 “Assessment of national and local practices”.</p>
Data format		MS Word (.docx), non-proprietary Unicode text format (.txt, .odt)

4	in progress	SINCRONY WP3 T3.3 Assessment of Deliberative and Participatory Practices with Youth in the UK V1
Data volume		5 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB
Accessibility		Excerpts: Open access (CC BY 4.0) Full data: Restricted access
Related publication/s		Not yet available

5	in progress	SINCRONY WP3 T3.3 Assessment of Deliberative and Participatory Practices with Youth in Portugal V1
ID [ID type]		Not yet available
Chosen repository		Closed access repository
Version		1.0
Team in charge		U.PORTO
Creator/s		Piedade, Filipe [U.PORTO];
Contributor/s		Menezes, Isabel [U.PORTO]; da Silva, Sofia Marques [U.PORTO]; Pais, Sofia Castanheira [U.PORTO]; Ferreira, Pedro [U.PORTO]; Ribeiro, Norberto [U.PORTO]; Costa, Ana [U.PORTO]; Piedade, Filipe [U.PORTO]
Contact Person/s		Menezes, Isabel [U.PORTO], imenezes@fpce.up.pt;
Contents		<p>This data set includes documents that led to the identification of 5 school and 10 community participation initiatives/projects recognized as good practices in Portugal. The documents contained in this data set are publicly available and include materials (written, graphical and/or video) and official documents (statutes, guidelines, internal rules, and protocols, reports, etc) that helped in characterizing the selected initiatives/projects. The data set also includes documents, produced by the SINCRONY Universidade do Porto research team, with the analysis of the previously mentioned materials and official documentation. This includes an analytical grid, including summary information about each initiative/project identified in Portugal.</p> <p>Qualitative data, based on thematic analysis, is generated in this task in order to understand:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What practices and experiences related to youth participation and deliberation are to be found across our countries of study 2. a) To what extent intersectional inclusion is considered in these practices, and how b) To what extent marginalised and excluded youth are recognised and involved in these practices? 3. The strengths and limitations for challenging systematic exclusion and power imbalances through youth participation and deliberation <p>Access to the data will be restricted in order to protect anonymity and prevent potential reputational harm related to the critical assessment</p>

5	in progress	<i>SINCRONY WP3 T3.3 Assessment of Deliberative and Participatory Practices with Youth in Portugal V1</i>
		of specific organisations and schools. Anonymized excerpts will be published via D3.2 “Assessment of national and local practices”.
Data format		MS Word (.docx), non-proprietary Unicode text format (.txt, .odt)
Data volume		5 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB
Accessibility		Excerpts: Open access (CC BY 4.0) Full data: Restricted access
Related publication/s		Not yet available

6	in progress	<i>SINCRONY WP3 T3.3 Assessment of Deliberative and Participatory Practices with Youth in Finland V1</i>
ID [ID type]		Not yet available
Chosen repository		Seafire, institutional repository of University of Turku, seafire.utu.fi
Version		1.0
Team in charge		UTU
Creator/s		Korventausta, Miikka [UTU]
Contributor/s		Setälä, Maija [UTU]; Leino, Mikko [UTU]; Huttunen, Janette [UTU]
Contact Person/s		Korventausta, Miikka [UTU], miikka.korventausta@utu.fi;
Contents		<p>This data set includes analytical description templates based on publicly available documents that led to the identification of 5 school and 10 community initiatives/projects recognized as good practices of deliberation/participation in Finland. The data contribute to evaluating existing Finnish deliberative and participatory practices. Qualitative data, based on thematic analysis, is generated in this task in order to understand:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What practices and experiences related to youth participation and deliberation are to be found across our countries of study 2. a) To what extent intersectional inclusion is considered in these practices, and how b) To what extent marginalised and excluded youth are recognised and involved in these practices? 3. The strengths and limitations for challenging systematic exclusion and power imbalances through youth participation and deliberation <p>Access to the data will be restricted in order to protect anonymity and prevent potential reputational harm related to the critical assessment of specific organisations and schools. Anonymized excerpts will be published via D3.2 “Assessment of national and local practices”.</p>
Data format		MS Word (.docx), non-proprietary Unicode text format (.txt, .odt)
Data volume		5 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB
Accessibility		Excerpts: Open access (CC BY 4.0)

6	in progress	SINCRONY WP3 T3.3 Assessment of Deliberative and Participatory Practices with Youth in Finland V1
		Full data: Restricted access
Related publication/s		Not yet available

7	in progress	SINCRONY WP3 T3.3 Cross-national Assessment of Deliberative and Participatory Practices with Youth V1
ID [ID type]		Not yet available
Chosen repository		Closed access repository
Version		1.0
Team in charge		UNIMAN
Creator/s		Pilkington, Hilary [UNIMAN]
Contributor/s		Mirshak, Nadim [UNIMAN]; Setälä, Maija [UTU]; Korventausta, Miikka [UTU]; Leino, Mikko [UTU]; Janette Huttunen [UTU]; Bruselius-Jensen, Maria [AAU]; Hansen da Cruz, Lika [AAU]; Dånge, Louise [AAU]; Helene Hoffmann, Jensen [AAU]; Albanesi, Cinzia [UNIBO]; Cicognani, Elvira [UNIBO]; Prati, Gabriele [UNIBO]; Tzankova, Iana I. [UNIBO]; Compare, Christian [UNIBO]; Guarino, Antonella [UNIBO]; Menezes, Isabel [U.PORTO]; da Silva, Sofia Marques [U.PORTO]; Pais, Sofia Castanheira [U.PORTO]; Ferreira, Pedro [U.PORTO]; Piedade, Filipe [U.PORTO]; Ribeiro, Norberto [U.PORTO], Costa, Ana [U.PORTO]
Contact Person/s		Pilkington, Hilary [UNIMAN], hilary.pilkington@manchester.ac.uk;
Contents		<p>Completion of five data description templates outlining documents of school and community initiatives/projects recognized as good practices of deliberation/participation in Denmark, Italy, the UK, Portugal and Finland, according to evaluation criteria provided by the Task lead. Qualitative data, based on thematic analysis, is generated in this task in order to understand:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What practices and experiences related to youth participation and deliberation are to be found across our countries of study 2. a) To what extent intersectional inclusion is considered in these practices, and how b) To what extent marginalised and excluded youth are recognised and involved in these practices? 3. The strengths and limitations for challenging systematic exclusion and power imbalances through youth participation and deliberation <p>Access to the data will be restricted in order to protect anonymity and prevent potential reputational harm related to the critical assessment of specific organisations and schools. Anonymized excerpts will be published via D3.2 “Assessment of national and local practices”.</p>

7	in progress	<i>SINCRONY WP3 T3.3 Cross-national Assessment of Deliberative and Participatory Practices with Youth V1</i>
Data format		MS Word (.docx), non-proprietary Unicode text format (.txt, .odt)
Data volume		5 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB
Accessibility		Excerpts: Open access (CC BY 4.0) Full data: Restricted access
Related publication/s		Not yet available

8	not yet available	<i>SINCRONY WP3 T3.4 Youth Inclusivity Footprint Database for Deliberative and Participative Processes V1</i>
ID [ID type]		Not yet available [To be determined]
Chosen repository		To be determined
Version		1.0
Team in charge		UTU
Creator/s		Setälä, Maija [UTU];
Contributor/s		Korventausta, Miikka [UTU]; Leino, Mikko [UTU]; Janette Huttunen [UTU]; Pilkington, Hilary [UNIMAN]; Mirshak, Nadim [UNIMAN]; Bruselius-Jensen, Maria [AAU]; Hansen da Cruz, Lika [AAU]; Dånge, Louise [AAU]; Helene Hoffmann, Jensen [AAU]; Albanesi, Cinzia [UNIBO]; Cicognani, Elvira [UNIBO]; Prati, Gabriele [UNIBO]; Tzankova, Iana I. [UNIBO]; Compare, Christian [UNIBO]; Guarino, Antonella [UNIBO]; Menezes, Isabel [U.PORTO]; da Silva, Sofia Marques [U.PORTO]; Pais, Sofia Castanheira [U.PORTO]; Ferreira, Pedro [U.PORTO]; Piedade, Filipe [U.PORTO]; Ribeiro, Norberto [U.PORTO], Costa, Ana [U.PORTO]
Contact Person/s		Korventausta, Miikka [UTU], miikka.korventausta@utu.fi;
Contents		To be determined
Data format		To be determined
Data volume		To be determined
Accessibility		Open access (CC BY 4.0)
Related publication/s		Not yet available

WP4 ASSESSMENT OF EXISTING PRACTICES IN AN INTERSECTIONAL LENS

WP4: WP4 analyses policy and policymakers' narratives on youth inclusion, power, and participation (Task 4.1) and young people's interaction with and counteraction to existing narratives on these issues (Task 4.2). The data help understand how political structures shape paths to political power and youth engagement, including marginalised youth. From an intersectional perspective, the analysis seeks to identify factors, processes, opportunities, and limitations of inclusive participation and deliberation with youth in an intersectional lens, providing significant recommendations for their meaningful inclusion in DPP.

Lead: UNIGE

Participants: AAU, UIBK, UNIBO, UNIGE, UNIMAN, U.PORTO, UTU, WEDO

Months: 4-16

Potential users for the datasets of this WP include researchers interested in participation and deliberation, as well as youth organizations, policymakers, youth workers, municipalities looking to understand young people's perspectives, their actions and reactions toward the different narratives that can be developed by political actors.

TASK 4.1 Analysis of social narratives on youth inclusion and participation in policies and among policymakers

9	in progress	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T4.1.1 Analysis of youth intersectional inclusion in EU policies V1</i>
ID [ID type]		Not yet available [DOI]
Chosen repository		Zenodo, https://zenodo.org FORS Center, https://forscenter.ch/data-services/
Version		1.0
Team in charge		UNIGE
Creator/s		Giugni, Marco [UNIGE]
Contributor/s		Holecz, Valentina [UNIGE]; Stojanović, Nenad [UNIGE]
Contact Person/s		Giugni, Marco [UNIGE], marco.giugni@unige.ch ;
Contents		The dataset consists of descriptive and analytical data of EU-level policy documents (e.g. laws, public programs, governmental reports). The data is generated from documents that are manually collected from public repositories and websites. Each of the policy documents is coded through content analysis aimed at evaluating whether and how intersectionality,

9	in progress	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T4.1.1 Analysis of youth intersectional inclusion in EU policies V1</i>
		inclusion and empowerment are recognized and addressed in relation to young people in EU policy. The dataset can be useful to researchers interested in comparing policy discourses on youth and/or participation and deliberation, as well as youth organizations, policymakers, youth workers, municipalities looking to understand the prevailing narratives on youth inclusion in participation and deliberation developed by political actors.
Data format		MS Excel (.xlsx), non-proprietary numerical tabular or comma-separated data (.txt, .csv)
Data volume		5 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB
Accessibility		Open access (CC BY 4.0)
Related publication/s		Not yet available

10	in progress	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T4.1.1 Analysis of youth intersectional inclusion in Danish policies V1</i>
ID [ID type]		Not yet available [DOI]
Chosen repository		Zenodo, https://zenodo.org
Version		1.0
Team in charge		AAU
Creator/s		Bruselius-Jensen, Maria [AAU];
Contributor/s		Hansen da Cruz, Lika [AAU]; Dånge, Louise [AAU]; Helene Hoffmann, Jensen [AAU]
Contact Person/s		Dånge, Louise [AAU], louiseba@ikl.aau.dk ;
Contents		The dataset consists of descriptive and analytical data of Danish policy documents (e.g. laws, public programs, governmental reports). The data is generated from documents that are manually collected from public repositories and websites. Each of the policy documents is coded through content analysis aimed at evaluating whether and how intersectionality, inclusion and empowerment are recognized and addressed in relation to young people in Danish policy. The dataset can be useful to researchers interested in comparing policy discourses on youth and/or participation and deliberation, as well as youth organizations, policymakers, youth workers, municipalities looking to understand the prevailing narratives on youth inclusion in participation and deliberation developed by political actors.
Data format		MS Excel (.xlsx), non-proprietary numerical tabular or comma-separated data (.txt, .csv)

10	in progress	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T4.1.1 Analysis of youth intersectional inclusion in Danish policies V1</i>
Data volume		5 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB
Accessibility		Open access (CC BY 4.0)
Related publication/s		Not yet available

11	in progress	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T4.1.1 Analysis of youth intersectional inclusion in Italian policies V1</i>
ID [ID type]		Not yet available [DOI]
Chosen repository		AMSActa, institutional repository of Alma Mater Studiorum – University of Bologna, https://amsacta.unibo.it
Version		1.0
Team in charge		UNIBO
Creator/s		Albanesi, Cinzia [UNIBO]
Contributor/s		Cicognani, Elvira [UNIBO]; Prati, Gabriele [UNIBO]; Tzankova, Iana I. [UNIBO]; Compare, Christian [UNIBO]; Guarino, Antonella [UNIBO]; Cecconi, Annalisa [UNIBO]
Contact Person/s		Tzankova, Iana I. [UNIBO], iana.tzankova2@unibo.it ;
Contents		<p>The dataset consists of descriptive and analytical data of Italian policy documents (e.g. laws, public programs, governmental reports). The data is generated from documents that are manually collected from public repositories and websites. Each of the policy documents is coded through content analysis aimed at evaluating whether and how intersectionality, inclusion and empowerment are recognized and addressed in relation to young people in Italian policy.</p> <p>The dataset can be useful to researchers interested in comparing policy discourses on youth and/or participation and deliberation, as well as youth organizations, policymakers, youth workers, municipalities looking to understand the prevailing narratives on youth inclusion in participation and deliberation developed by political actors.</p>
Data format		MS Excel (.xlsx), non-proprietary numerical tabular or comma-separated data (.txt, .csv)
Data volume		5 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB
Accessibility		Open access (CC BY 4.0)
Related publication/s		Not yet available

12	in progress	SINCRONY WP4 T4.1.1 Analysis of youth intersectional inclusion in Swiss policies V1
ID [ID type]		Not yet available [DOI]
Chosen repository		Zenodo, https://zenodo.org FORS Center, https://forscenter.ch/data-services/
Version		1.0
Team in charge		UNIGE
Creator/s		Giugni, Marco [UNIGE]
Contributor/s		Holecz, Valentina [UNIGE]; Stojanović, Nenad [UNIGE]
Contact Person/s		Giugni, Marco [UNIGE], marco.giugni@unige.ch ;
Contents		<p>The dataset consists of descriptive and analytical data of Swiss policy documents (e.g. laws, public programs, governmental reports). The data is generated from documents that are manually collected from public repositories and websites. Each of the policy documents is coded through content analysis aimed at evaluating whether and how intersectionality, inclusion and empowerment are recognized and addressed in relation to young people in Swiss policy.</p> <p>The dataset can be useful to researchers interested in comparing policy discourses on youth and/or participation and deliberation, as well as youth organizations, policymakers, youth workers, municipalities looking to understand the prevailing narratives on youth inclusion in participation and deliberation developed by political actors.</p>
Data format		Data collection/generation/processing (raw data): MS Excel (.xlsx); Data preservation and sharing: MS Excel (.xlsx), non-proprietary numerical tabular or comma-separated data (.txt, .csv)
Data volume		5 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB
Accessibility		Open access (CC BY 4.0)
Related publication/s		Not yet available

13	in progress	SINCRONY WP4 T4.1.1 Analysis of youth intersectional inclusion in UK policies V1
ID [ID type]		Not yet available [DOI]
Chosen repository		Figshare, https://figshare.com
Version		1.0
Team in charge		UNIMAN

13	in progress	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T4.1.1 Analysis of youth intersectional inclusion in UK policies V1</i>
Creator/s		Pilkington, Hilary [UNIMAN];
Contributor/s		Mirshak, Nadim [UNIMAN];
Contact Person/s		Pilkington, Hilary [UNIMAN], hilary.pilkington@manchester.ac.uk;
Contents		<p>The dataset consists of descriptive and analytical data of UK policy documents (e.g. laws, public programs, governmental reports). The data is generated from documents that are manually collected from public repositories and websites. Each of the policy documents is coded through content analysis aimed at evaluating whether and how intersectionality, inclusion and empowerment are recognized and addressed in relation to young people in UK policy.</p> <p>The dataset can be useful to researchers interested in comparing policy discourses on youth and/or participation and deliberation, as well as youth organizations, policymakers, youth workers, municipalities looking to understand the prevailing narratives on youth inclusion in participation and deliberation developed by political actors.</p>
Data format		MS Excel (.xlsx), non-proprietary numerical tabular or comma-separated data (.txt, .csv)
Data volume		5 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB
Accessibility		Open access (CC BY 4.0)
Related publication/s		Not yet available

14	in progress	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T4.1.1 Analysis of youth intersectional inclusion in Portuguese policies V1</i>
ID [ID type]		Not yet available [DOI]
Chosen repository		Zenodo, https://zenodo.org
Version		1.0
Team in charge		U.PORTO
Creator/s		Piedade, Filipe [U.PORTO];
Contributor/s		Menezes, Isabel [U.PORTO]; da Silva, Sofia Marques [U.PORTO]; Pais, Sofia Castanheira [U.PORTO]; Ferreira, Pedro [U.PORTO]; Costa, Ana [U.PORTO], Piedade, Filipe [U.PORTO]
Contact Person/s		da Silva, Sofia Marques [U.PORTO]; sofiamsilva@fpce.up.pt;
Contents		The dataset consists of descriptive and analytical data of Portuguese policy documents (e.g. laws, public programs, governmental reports). The

14	in progress	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T4.1.1 Analysis of youth intersectional inclusion in Portuguese policies V1</i>
		<p>data is generated from documents that are manually collected from public repositories and websites. Each of the policy documents is coded through content analysis aimed at evaluating whether and how intersectionality, inclusion and empowerment are recognized and addressed in relation to young people in EU policy.</p> <p>The dataset can be useful to researchers interested in comparing policy discourses on youth and/or participation and deliberation, as well as youth organizations, policymakers, youth workers, municipalities looking to understand the prevailing narratives on youth inclusion in participation and deliberation developed by political actors.</p>
Data format		MS Excel (.xlsx), non-proprietary numerical tabular or comma-separated data (.txt, .csv)
Data volume		5 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB
Accessibility		Open access (CC BY 4.0)
Related publication/s		Not yet available

15	in progress	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T4.1.1 Analysis of youth intersectional inclusion in Finnish policies V1</i>
ID [ID type]		Not yet available [DOI]
Chosen repository		Zenodo, https://zenodo.org
Version		1.0
Team in charge		UTU
Creator/s		Korventausta, Miikka [UTU]
Contributor/s		Huttunen, Janette [UTU], Setälä, Maija [UTU], Leino, Mikko [UTU]
Contact Person/s		Korventausta, Miikka [UTU], miikka.korventausta@utu.fi ;
Contents		<p>The dataset consists of descriptive and analytical data of Finnish policy documents (e.g. laws, public programs, governmental reports). The data is generated from documents that are manually collected from public repositories and websites. Each of the policy documents is coded through content analysis aimed at evaluating whether and how intersectionality, inclusion and empowerment are recognized and addressed in relation to young people in EU policy.</p> <p>The dataset can be useful to researchers interested in comparing policy discourses on youth and/or participation and deliberation, as well as youth organizations, policymakers, youth workers, municipalities looking to understand the prevailing narratives on youth inclusion in participation and deliberation developed by political actors.</p>

15	in progress	SINCRONY WP4 T4.1.1 Analysis of youth intersectional inclusion in Finnish policies V1
Data format		MS Excel (.xlsx), non-proprietary numerical tabular or comma-separated data (.txt, .csv)
Data volume		5 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB
Accessibility		Open access (CC BY 4.0)
Related publication/s		Not yet available

16	in progress	SINCRONY WP4 T4.1.1 Cross-national analysis of youth intersectional inclusion in policies V1
ID [ID type]		Not yet available [DOI]
Chosen repository		Zenodo, https://zenodo.org FORS Center, https://forscenter.ch/data-services/
Version		1.0
Team in charge		UNIGE
Creator/s		Giugni, Marco [UNIGE]
Contributor/s		Holecz, Valentina [UNIGE]; Stojanović, Nenad [UNIGE]; Bruselius-Jensen, Maria [AAU]; Hansen da Cruz, Lika [AAU]; Dånge, Louise [AAU]; Helene Hoffmann, Jensen [AAU]; Albanesi, Cinzia [UNIBO]; Cicognani, Elvira [UNIBO]; Prati, Gabriele [UNIBO]; Tzankova, Iana I. [UNIBO]; Compare, Christian [UNIBO]; Guarino, Antonella [UNIBO]; Cecconi, Annalisa [UNIBO]; Pilkington, Hilary [UNIMAN]; Mirshak, Nadim [UNIMAN]; Menezes, Isabel [U.PORTO]; da Silva, Sofia Marques [U.PORTO]; Pais, Sofia Castanheira [U.PORTO]; Ferreira, Pedro [U.PORTO]; Ribeiro, Norberto [U.PORTO], Costa, Ana [U.PORTO], Piedade, Filipe [U.PORTO]; Setälä, Maija [UTU]; Korventausta, Miikka [UTU]; Huttunen, Janette [UTU];
Contact Person/s		Giugni, Marco [UNIGE], marco.giugni@unige.ch;
Contents		<p>The dataset consists of descriptive and analytical data of policy documents (e.g. laws, public programs, governmental reports) in Denmark, Italy, Switzerland, the UK, Portugal and Finland. The data is generated from documents that are manually collected from public repositories and websites. Each of the policy documents is coded through content analysis aimed at evaluating whether and how intersectionality, inclusion and empowerment are recognized and addressed in relation to young people in the policies.</p> <p>The dataset can be useful to researchers interested in comparing policy discourses on youth and/or participation and deliberation, as well as youth organizations, policymakers, youth workers, municipalities looking to</p>

16	in progress	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T4.1.1 Cross-national analysis of youth intersectional inclusion in policies V1</i>
		understand the prevailing narratives on youth inclusion in participation and deliberation developed by political actors.
Data format		MS Excel (.xlsx), non-proprietary numerical tabular or comma-separated data (.txt, .csv)
Data volume		5 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB
Accessibility		Open access (CC BY 4.0)
Related publication/s		Not yet available

17	in progress	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T4.1.2 Analysis of youth intersectional inclusion in EU policymakers' social media V1</i>
ID [ID type]	Not yet available [DOI]	
Chosen repository	Zenodo, https://zenodo.org FORS Center, https://forscenter.ch/data-services/	
Version	1.0	
Team in charge	UNIGE	
Creator/s	Giugni, Marco [UNIGE]	
Contributor/s	Holecz, Valentina [UNIGE]; Stojanović, Nenad [UNIGE]	
Contact Person/s	Giugni, Marco [UNIGE], marco.giugni@unige.ch ;	
Contents	<p>The dataset consists of data from the analysis of Instagram channels of EU policymakers: analytical grid containing links to the analysed posts and descriptions of date, format, interactions, object, issue, tone, inclusion and empowerment.</p> <p>Access to this data may be restricted due to the personal nature of data included in social media channels.</p> <p>The dataset can be useful to researchers interested in social media discourses on youth and/or participation and deliberation, as well as youth organizations, policymakers, youth workers, municipalities looking to understand the prevailing narratives on youth inclusion in participation and deliberation developed by political actors.</p>	
Data format	MS Word (.docx), non-proprietary Unicode text format (.txt, .odt)	
Data volume	5 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB	
Accessibility	Not yet defined	
Related publication/s	Not yet available	

18	in progress	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T4.1.2 Analysis of youth intersectional inclusion in Danish policymakers' social media V1</i>
ID [ID type]	Not yet available [DOI]	
Chosen repository	Zenodo, https://zenodo.org	
Version	1.0	
Team in charge	AAU	
Creator/s	Bruselius-Jensen, Maria [AAU];	
Contributor/s	Hansen da Cruz, Lika [AAU]; Dånge, Louise [AAU]	

18	in progress	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T4.1.2 Analysis of youth intersectional inclusion in Danish policymakers' social media V1</i>
Contact Person/s		Dånge, Louise [AAU], louseba@ikl.aau.dk;
Contents		<p>The dataset consists of data from the analysis of Instagram channels of 4 national and local Danish political parties or policymakers: links to the analysed posts and analytical grid containing links to the analysed posts and descriptions of date, format, interactions, object, issue, tone, inclusion and empowerment.</p> <p>Access to this data may be restricted due to the personal nature of data included in social media channels.</p> <p>The dataset can be useful to researchers interested in social media discourses on youth and/or participation and deliberation, as well as youth organizations, policymakers, youth workers, municipalities looking to understand the prevailing narratives on youth inclusion in participation and deliberation developed by political actors.</p>
Data format		MS Word (.docx), non-proprietary Unicode text format (.txt, .odt)
Data volume		5 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB
Accessibility		Not yet defined
Related publication/s		Not yet available

19	in progress	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T4.1.2 Analysis of youth intersectional inclusion in Italian policymakers' social media V1</i>
ID [ID type]		Not yet available [DOI]
Chosen repository		AMSActa, institutional repository of Alma Mater Studiorum – University of Bologna, https://amsacta.unibo.it
Version		1.0
Team in charge		UNIBO
Creator/s		Albanesi, Cinzia [UNIBO]
Contributor/s		Cicognani, Elvira [UNIBO]; Prati, Gabriele [UNIBO]; Tzankova, Iana I. [UNIBO]; Compare, Christian [UNIBO]; Guarino, Antonella [UNIBO];
Contact Person/s		Guarino, Antonella [UNIBO], antonella.guarino2@unibo.it
Contents		<p>The dataset consists of data from the analysis of Instagram channels of 4 national and local Danish political parties or policymakers: analytical grid containing links to the analysed posts and descriptions of date, format, interactions, object, issue, tone, inclusion and empowerment.</p> <p>Access to this data may be restricted due to the personal nature of data included in social media channels.</p>

19	in progress	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T4.1.2 Analysis of youth intersectional inclusion in Italian policymakers' social media V1</i>
		The dataset can be useful to researchers interested in social media discourses on youth and/or participation and deliberation, as well as youth organizations, policymakers, youth workers, municipalities looking to understand the prevailing narratives on youth inclusion in participation and deliberation developed by political actors.
Data format		MS Word (.docx), non-proprietary Unicode text format (.txt, .odt)
Data volume		5 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB
Accessibility		Not yet defined
Related publication/s		Not yet available

20	in progress	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T4.1.2 Analysis of youth intersectional inclusion in Swiss policymakers' social media V1</i>
ID [ID type]		Not yet available [DOI]
Chosen repository		Zenodo, https://zenodo.org FORS Center, https://forscenter.ch/data-services/
Version		1.0
Team in charge		UNIGE
Creator/s		Giugni, Marco [UNIGE]
Contributor/s		Holecz, Valentina [UNIGE]; Stojanović, Nenad [UNIGE]
Contact Person/s		Giugni, Marco [UNIGE], marco.giugni@unige.ch ;
Contents		<p>The dataset consists of data from the analysis of Instagram channels of 4 national and local Swiss political parties or policymakers: analytical grid containing links to the analysed posts and descriptions of date, format, interactions, object, issue, tone, inclusion and empowerment. Access to this data may be restricted due to the personal nature of data included in social media channels.</p> <p>The dataset can be useful to researchers interested in social media discourses on youth and/or participation and deliberation, as well as youth organizations, policymakers, youth workers, municipalities looking to understand the prevailing narratives on youth inclusion in participation and deliberation developed by political actors.</p>
Data format		MS Word (.docx), non-proprietary Unicode text format (.txt, .odt)
Data volume		5 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB
Accessibility		Not yet defined
Related publication/s		Not yet available

21	in progress	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T4.1.2 Analysis of youth intersectional inclusion in UK policymakers' social media V1</i>
ID [ID type]		Not yet available [DOI]
Chosen repository		Figshare, https://figshare.com
Version		1.0
Team in charge		UNIMAN
Creator/s		Pilkington, Hilary [UNIMAN];
Contributor/s		Mirshak, Nadim [UNIMAN];
Contact Person/s		Pilkington, Hilary [UNIMAN], hilary.pilkington@manchester.ac.uk ;
Contents		<p>The dataset consists of data from the analysis of Instagram channels of 4 national and local UK political parties or policymakers: analytical grid containing links to the analysed posts and descriptions of date, format, interactions, object, issue, tone, inclusion and empowerment. Access to this data may be restricted due to the personal nature of data included in social media channels.</p> <p>The dataset can be useful to researchers interested in social media discourses on youth and/or participation and deliberation, as well as youth organizations, policymakers, youth workers, municipalities looking to understand the prevailing narratives on youth inclusion in participation and deliberation developed by political actors.</p>
Data format		MS Word (.docx), non-proprietary Unicode text format (.txt, .odt)
Data volume		5 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB
Accessibility		Not yet defined
Related publication/s		Not yet available

22	in progress	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T4.1.2 Analysis of youth intersectional inclusion in Portuguese policymakers' social media V1</i>
ID [ID type]		Not yet available [DOI]
Chosen repository		Zenodo, https://zenodo.org
Version		1.0
Team in charge		U.PORTO
Creator/s		Piedade, Filipe [U.PORTO];

22	in progress	SINCRONY WP4 T4.1.2 Analysis of youth intersectional inclusion in Portuguese policymakers' social media V1
Contributor/s	Menezes, Isabel [U.PORTO]; da Silva, Sofia Marques [U.PORTO]; Pais, Sofia Castanheira [U.PORTO]; Ferreira, Pedro [U.PORTO]; Ribeiro, Norberto [U.PORTO], Costa, Ana [U.PORTO]; Piedade, Filipe [U.PORTO]	
Contact Person/s	da Silva, Sofia Marques [U.PORTO]; sofiamsilva@fpce.up.pt;	
Contents	<p>The dataset consists of data from the analysis of Instagram channels of 4 national and local Portuguese political parties or policymakers: analytical grid containing links to the analysed posts and descriptions of date, format, interactions, object, issue, tone, inclusion and empowerment. Access to this data may be restricted due to the personal nature of data included in social media channels.</p> <p>The dataset can be useful to researchers interested in social media discourses on youth and/or participation and deliberation, as well as youth organizations, policymakers, youth workers, municipalities looking to understand the prevailing narratives on youth inclusion in participation and deliberation developed by political actors.</p>	
Data format	MS Word (.docx), non-proprietary Unicode text format (.txt, .odt)	
Data volume	5 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB	
Accessibility	Not yet defined	
Related publication/s	Not yet available	

23	in progress	SINCRONY WP4 T4.1.2 Analysis of youth intersectional inclusion in Finnish policymakers' social media V1
ID [ID type]	Not yet available [DOI]	
Chosen repository	Zenodo, https://zenodo.org	
Version	1.0	
Team in charge	UTU	
Creator/s	Korventausta, Miikka [UTU]	
Contributor/s	Huttunen, Janette [UTU], Leino, Mikko [UTU], Setälä, Maija [UTU]	
Contact Person/s	Korventausta, Miikka [UTU], miikka.korventausta@utu.fi;	
Contents	The dataset consists of data from the analysis of Instagram channels of 4 national and local Finnish political parties or policymakers: analytical grid containing links to the analysed posts and descriptions of date, format, interactions, object, issue, tone, inclusion and empowerment.	

23	in progress	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T4.1.2 Analysis of youth intersectional inclusion in Finnish policymakers' social media V1</i>
		<p>Access to this data may be restricted due to the personal nature of data included in social media channels.</p> <p>The dataset can be useful to researchers interested in social media discourses on youth and/or participation and deliberation, as well as youth organizations, policymakers, youth workers, municipalities looking to understand the prevailing narratives on youth inclusion in participation and deliberation developed by political actors.</p>
Data format		MS Word (.docx), non-proprietary Unicode text format (.txt, .odt)
Data volume		5 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB
Accessibility		Not yet defined
Related publication/s		Not yet available

24	in progress	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T4.1.2 Cross-national analysis of youth intersectional inclusion in policymakers' social media V1</i>
ID [ID type]		Not yet available [DOI]
Chosen repository		Zenodo, https://zenodo.org FORS Center, https://forscenter.ch/data-services/
Version		1.0
Team in charge		UNIGE
Creator/s		Giugni, Marco [UNIGE]
Contributor/s		Holecz, Valentina [UNIGE]; Stojanović, Nenad [UNIGE]; Bruselius-Jensen, Maria [AAU]; Hansen da Cruz, Lika [AAU]; Dånge, Louise [AAU]; Albanesi, Cinzia [UNIBO]; Cicognani, Elvira [UNIBO]; Prati, Gabriele [UNIBO]; Tzankova, Iana I. [UNIBO]; Compare, Christian [UNIBO]; Guarino, Antonella [UNIBO]; Pilkington, Hilary [UNIMAN]; Mirshak, Nadim [UNIMAN]; Menezes, Isabel [U.PORTO]; da Silva, Sofia Marques [U.PORTO]; Pais, Sofia Castanheira [U.PORTO]; Ferreira, Pedro [U.PORTO]; Ribeiro, Norberto [U.PORTO], Costa, Ana [U.PORTO]; Piedade, Filipe [U.PORTO]; Setälä, Maija [UTU]; Korventausta, Miikka [UTU]; Huttunen, Janette [UTU]; Leino, Mikko [UTU]
Contact Person/s		Giugni, Marco [UNIGE], marco.giugni@unige.ch;
Contents		The dataset consists of data from the cross-national analysis of Instagram channels of national and local political parties or policymakers in Denmark, Italy, Switzerland, the UK, Portugal and Finland: analytical grid containing links to the analysed posts and descriptions of date, format, interactions, object, issue, tone, inclusion and empowerment.

24	in progress	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T4.1.2 Cross-national analysis of youth intersectional inclusion in policymakers' social media V1</i>
		<p>Access to this data may be restricted due to the personal nature of data included in social media channels.</p> <p>The dataset can be useful to researchers interested in social media discourses on youth and/or participation and deliberation, as well as youth organizations, policymakers, youth workers, municipalities looking to understand the prevailing narratives on youth inclusion in participation and deliberation developed by political actors.</p>
Data format		MS Word (.docx), non-proprietary Unicode text format (.txt, .odt)
Data volume		5 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB
Accessibility		Not yet defined
Related publication/s		Not yet available

Task 4.2 Analysis of how youth interact with and counteract existing narratives about inclusion and participation: Mixed methods research

25	in progress	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T4.2.1 Analysis of participation narratives in youth social media in Denmark V1</i>
ID [ID type]		Not yet available [DOI]
Chosen repository		Zenodo, https://zenodo.org
Version		1.0
Team in charge		AAU
Creator/s		Bruselius-Jensen, Maria [AAU];
Contributor/s		Hansen da Cruz, Lika [AAU]; Dånge, Louise [AAU]
Contact Person/s		Dånge, Louise [AAU], louiseba@ikl.aau.dk ;
Contents		<p>The data is based on publicly available visual and text material from social media profiles (Instagram) of 2 youth organizations in Denmark. However, the visual files will not be saved as data. Instead, each partner will do an analysis of the organizations' Instagram posts, and write down their analysis and codings in a word document. In this word document, they will include a link to each post they analyze. These word documents with the data analysis and links to the posts which are analysed, will be made available at Zenodo.</p> <p>Access to this data may be restricted due to the personal nature of data included in social media channels.</p> <p>The dataset can be useful to researchers interested in social media discourses on youth and/or participation and deliberation, as well as youth organizations, policymakers, youth workers, municipalities looking to understand the prevailing narratives on inclusion in participation and deliberation from young people's perspectives.</p>
Data format		MS Word (.docx), non-proprietary Unicode text format (.txt, .odt)
Data volume		5 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB
Accessibility		Not yet defined
Related publication/s		Not yet available

26	in progress	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T4.2.1 Analysis of participation narratives in youth social media in Italy V1</i>
ID [ID type]		Not yet available [DOI]
Chosen repository		AMSActa, institutional repository of Alma Mater Studiorum – University of Bologna, https://amsacta.unibo.it

26	in progress	SINCRONY WP4 T4.2.1 Analysis of participation narratives in youth social media in Italy V1
Version		1.0
Team in charge		UNIBO
Creator/s		Albanesi, Cinzia [UNIBO]
Contributor/s		Cicognani, Elvira [UNIBO]; Prati, Gabriele [UNIBO]; Tzankova, Iana I. [UNIBO]; Compare, Christian [UNIBO]; Guarino, Antonella [UNIBO]; Lorusso, Maric Martin [UNIBO]
Contact Person/s		Albanesi, Cinzia [UNIBO], cinzia.albanesi@unibo.it;
Contents		<p>The data is based on publicly available visual and text material from social media profiles of 2 youth organizations in Italy: However, the visual files will not be saved as data. Instead, each partner will do an analysis of the organizations' Instagram posts, and write down their analysis and codings in a word document. In this word document, they will include a link to each post they analyze. These word documents with the data analysis and links to the posts which are analysed, will be made available at AMSacta. Access to this data may be restricted due to the personal nature of data included in social media channels.</p> <p>The dataset can be useful to researchers interested in social media discourses on youth and/or participation and deliberation, as well as youth organizations, policymakers, youth workers, municipalities looking to understand the prevailing narratives on inclusion in participation and deliberation from young people's perspectives.</p>
Data format		MS Word (.docx), non-proprietary Unicode text format (.txt, .odt)
Data volume		5 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB
Accessibility		Not yet defined
Related publication/s		Not yet available

27	in progress	SINCRONY WP4 T4.2.1 Analysis of participation narratives in youth social media in Switzerland V1
ID [ID type]		Not yet available [DOI]
Chosen repository		Zenodo, https://zenodo.org FORS Center, https://forscenter.ch/data-services/
Version		1.0
Team in charge		UNIGE
Creator/s		Giugni, Marco [UNIGE]

27	in progress	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T4.2.1 Analysis of participation narratives in youth social media in Switzerland V1</i>
Contributor/s		Holecz, Valentina [UNIGE]; Stojanović, Nenad [UNIGE]
Contact Person/s		Giugni, Marco [UNIGE], marco.giugni@unige.ch;
Contents		<p>The data is based on publicly available visual and text material from social media profiles of 2 youth organizations in Switzerland: However, the visual files will not be saved as data. Instead, each partner will do an analysis of the organizations' Instagram posts, and write down their analysis and codings in a word document. In this word document, they will include a link to each post they analyze. These word documents with the data analysis and links to the posts which are analysed, will be made available at Zenodo.</p> <p>Access to this data may be restricted due to the personal nature of data included in social media channels.</p> <p>The dataset can be useful to researchers interested in social media discourses on youth and/or participation and deliberation, as well as youth organizations, policymakers, youth workers, municipalities looking to understand the prevailing narratives on inclusion in participation and deliberation from young people's perspectives.</p>
Data format		MS Word (.docx), non-proprietary Unicode text format (.txt, .odt)
Data volume		5 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB
Accessibility		Not yet defined
Related publication/s		Not yet available

28	in progress	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T4.2.1 Analysis of participation narratives in youth social media in the UK V1</i>
ID [ID type]		Not yet available [DOI]
Chosen repository		Figshare, https://figshare.com
Version		1.0
Team in charge		UNIMAN
Creator/s		Pilkington, Hilary [UNIMAN];
Contributor/s		Mirshak, Nadim [UNIMAN];
Contact Person/s		Pilkington, Hilary [UNIMAN], hilary.pilkington@manchester.ac.uk;
Contents		The data is based on publicly available visual and text material from social media profiles (Instagram) of 2 youth organizations in the UK. However, the visual files will not be saved as data. Instead, each partner will do an

28	in progress	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T4.2.1 Analysis of participation narratives in youth social media in the UK V1</i>
		<p>analysis of the organizations' Instagram posts, and write down their analysis and codings in a word document. In this word document, they will include a link to each post they analyze. These word documents with the data analysis and links to the posts which are analysed, will be made available at Figshare.</p> <p>Access to this data may be restricted due to the personal nature of data included in social media channels.</p> <p>The dataset can be useful to researchers interested in social media discourses on youth and/or participation and deliberation, as well as youth organizations, policymakers, youth workers, municipalities looking to understand the prevailing narratives on inclusion in participation and deliberation from young people's perspectives.</p>
Data format		MS Word (.docx), non-proprietary Unicode text format (.txt, .odt)
Data volume		5 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB
Accessibility		Not yet defined
Related publication/s		Not yet available

29	in progress	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T4.2.1 Analysis of participation narratives in youth social media in Portugal V1</i>
ID [ID type]		Not yet available [DOI]
Chosen repository		Zenodo, https://zenodo.org
Version		1.0
Team in charge		U.PORTO
Creator/s		Piedade, Filipe [U.PORTO];
Contributor/s		Menezes, Isabel [U.PORTO]; da Silva, Sofia Marques [U.PORTO]; Pais, Sofia Castanheira [U.PORTO]; Ferreira, Pedro [U.PORTO]; Ribeiro, Norberto [U.PORTO], Costa, Ana [U.PORTO], Piedade, Filipe [U.PORTO]
Contact Person/s		da Silva, Sofia Marques [U.PORTO]; sofiamsilva@fpce.up.pt ;
Contents		The data is based on publicly available visual and text material from social media profiles of 2 youth organizations in Portugal: However, the visual files will not be saved as data. Instead, each partner will do an analysis of the organizations' Instagram posts, and write down their analysis and codings in a word document. In this word document, they will include a link to each post they analyze. These word documents with the data analysis and links to the posts which are analysed, will be made available at Zenodo.

29	in progress	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T4.2.1 Analysis of participation narratives in youth social media in Portugal V1</i>
		<p>Access to this data may be restricted due to the personal nature of data included in social media channels.</p> <p>The dataset can be useful to researchers interested in social media discourses on youth and/or participation and deliberation, as well as youth organizations, policymakers, youth workers, municipalities looking to understand the prevailing narratives on inclusion in participation and deliberation from young people's perspectives.</p>
Data format		MS Word (.docx), non-proprietary Unicode text format (.txt, .odt)
Data volume		5 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB
Accessibility		Not yet defined
Related publication/s		Not yet available

30	in progress	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T4.2.1 Analysis of participation narratives in youth social media in Finland V1</i>
ID [ID type]		Not yet available [DOI]
Chosen repository		Zenodo, https://zenodo.org
Version		1.0
Team in charge		UTU
Creator/s		Korventausta, Miikka [UTU]
Contributor/s		Huttunen, Janette [UTU], Setälä, Maija [UTU], Leino, Mikko [UTU]
Contact Person/s		Korventausta, Miikka [UTU], miikka.korventausta@utu.fi ;
Contents		<p>The data is based on publicly available visual and text material from social media profiles of 2 youth organizations in Finland: However, the visual files will not be saved as data. Instead, each partner will do an analysis of the organizations' Instagram posts, and write down their analysis and codings in a word document. In this word document, they will include a link to each post they analyze. These word documents with the data analysis and links to the posts which are analysed, will be made available at Zenodo.</p> <p>Access to this data may be restricted due to the personal nature of data included in social media channels.</p> <p>The dataset can be useful to researchers interested in social media discourses on youth and/or participation and deliberation, as well as youth organizations, policymakers, youth workers, municipalities looking to understand the prevailing narratives on inclusion in participation and deliberation from young people's perspectives.</p>

30	in progress	SINCRONY WP4 T4.2.1 Analysis of participation narratives in youth social media in Finland V1
Data format		MS Word (.docx), non-proprietary Unicode text format (.txt, .odt)
Data volume		5 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB
Accessibility		Not yet defined
Related publication/s		Not yet available

31	in progress	SINCRONY WP4 T4.2.1 Cross-national analysis of participation narratives in youth social media V1
ID [ID type]		Not yet available [DOI]
Chosen repository		Zenodo, https://zenodo.org
Version		1.0
Team in charge		AAU
Creator/s		Bruselius-Jensen, Maria [AAU];
Contributor/s		Hansen da Cruz, Lika [AAU]; Dånge, Louise [AAU]; Albanesi, Cinzia [UNIBO]; Cicognani, Elvira [UNIBO]; Prati, Gabriele [UNIBO]; Tzankova, Iana I. [UNIBO]; Compare, Christian [UNIBO]; Guarino, Antonella [UNIBO]; Lorusso, Maric Martin [UNIBO]; Giugni, Marco [UNIGE]; Holecz, Valentina [UNIGE]; Stojanović, Nenad [UNIGE]; Pilkington, Hilary [UNIMAN]; Mirshak, Nadim [UNIMAN]; Menezes, Isabel [U.PORTO]; da Silva, Sofia Marques [U.PORTO]; Pais, Sofia Castanheira [U.PORTO]; Ferreira, Pedro [U.PORTO]; Ribeiro, Norberto [U.PORTO], Costa, Ana [U.PORTO], Piedade, Filipe [U.PORTO]; Setälä, Maija [UTU]; Korventausta, Miikka [UTU]; Huttunen, Janette [UTU]; Leino, Mikko [UTU]
Contact Person/s		Dånge, Louise [AAU], louiseba@ikl.aau.dk ;
Contents		<p>The data is based on available visual and text material from social media profiles of 12 youth organizations in Denmark, Italy, Switzerland, the UK, Portugal and Finland: analytical grid containing descriptions of the organizations' profile, main content issues and forms of communication, in-depth analysis of selected posts assessing aims, agency, intersectionality. Screenshots from Instagram posts related to youth might be included in the technical report.</p> <p>Access to this data may be restricted due to the personal nature of data included in social media channels.</p> <p>The dataset can be useful to researchers interested in social media discourses on youth and/or participation and deliberation, as well as youth organizations, policymakers, youth workers, municipalities looking to</p>

31	in progress	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T4.2.1 Cross-national analysis of participation narratives in youth social media V1</i>
		understand the prevailing narratives on inclusion in participation and deliberation from young people's perspectives.
Data format		MS Word (.docx), non-proprietary Unicode text format (.txt, .odt)
Data volume		5 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB
Accessibility		Not yet defined
Related publication/s		Not yet available

32	in progress	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T4.2.2 Survey of youth experience of intersectional exclusion and inclusion among school students in Denmark V1</i>
ID [ID type]	Not yet available [DOI]	
Chosen repository	Zenodo, https://zenodo.org	
Version	1.0	
Team in charge	AAU	
Creator/s	Bruselius-Jensen, Maria [AAU];	
Contributor/s	Hansen da Cruz, Lika [AAU]; Dånge, Louise [AAU]	
Contact Person/s	Dånge, Louise [AAU], louiseba@ikl.aau.dk ;	
Contents	<p>Data collected in schools in Denmark through an anonymous survey. The dataset contains demographic data that are relevant in an intersectional perspective, e.g. migration background, SES, religion, political orientation, sexual orientation and identity, disability etc. These questions are crucial for the project as they represent important basis for understanding experiences of exclusion and marginalization based on categories of belonging or power unbalance.</p> <p>It also contains quantitative data regarding experiences of exclusion (e.g., Sternthal et al. scale, 2011), discrimination in examination contexts (e.g. school and community), social justice orientation (e.g. scale of Torres-Harding et al. 2012); participation experiences (cf. Enchikova et al. 2019) and quality of participation in schools, within organisations (Ferreira et al. 2012) and in deliberation processes (Nabatchi, 2007). Empowerment (Peterson et al., 2006; Speer et al., 2019), trust in institutions (Grootaert, 2004) and sense of belonging (Slaten et al., 2019). Data are collected using psychometrically validated scales.</p> <p>The data can be reused by researchers who want to compare it with similar data collected at other points in historical time as well as in other countries. Likewise, stakeholders may be interested in reanalyzing the data particularly with a focus on youth participation and deliberation in schools.</p>	
Data format	SPSS statistical data (.sav, .dat, .sps), Microsoft Excel (.xls/.xlsx), non-proprietary numerical tabular data (.csv)	
Data volume	5 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB	
Accessibility	Open access (CC BY 4.0)	
Related publication/s	Not yet available	

33	in progress	SINCRONY WP4 T4.2.2 Survey of youth experience of intersectional exclusion and inclusion among organisation members in Denmark V1
ID [ID type]	Not yet available [DOI]	
Chosen repository	Zenodo, https://zenodo.org	
Version	1.0	
Team in charge	AAU	
Creator/s	Bruselius-Jensen, Maria [AAU];	
Contributor/s	Hansen da Cruz, Lika [AAU]; Dånge, Louise [AAU]	
Contact Person/s	Dånge, Louise [AAU], louiseba@ikl.aau.dk ;	
Contents	<p>Data collected among members of youth organisations and groups in Denmark through anonymous survey. The dataset contains demographic data that are relevant in an intersectional perspective, e.g. migration background, SES, religion, political orientation, sexual orientation and identity, disability etc. These questions are crucial for the project as they represent important basis for understanding experiences of exclusion and marginalization based on categories of belonging or power unbalance. It also contains quantitative data regarding experiences of exclusion (e.g., Sternthal et al. scale, 2011), discrimination in examination contexts (e.g. school and community), social justice orientation (e.g. scale of Torres-Harding et al. 2012); participation experiences (cf. Enchikova et al. 2019) and quality of participation within organisations (Ferreira et al. 2012) and in deliberation processes (Nabatchi, 2007). Empowerment (Peterson et al., 2006; Speer et al., 2019), trust in institutions (Grootaert, 2004) and sense of belonging (Slaten et al., 2019). Data are collected using psychometrically validated scales.</p> <p>The data can be reused by researchers who want to compare it with similar data collected at other points in historical time as well as in other countries. Likewise, stakeholders may be interested in reanalyzing the data particularly with a focus on youth participation and deliberation in communities.</p>	
Data format	SPSS statistical data (.sav, .dat, .sps), Microsoft Excel (.xls/.xlsx), non-proprietary numerical tabular data (.csv)	
Data volume	5 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB	
Accessibility	Open access (CC BY 4.0)	
Related publication/s	Not yet available	

34	in progress	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T4.2.2 Survey of youth experience of intersectional exclusion and inclusion among school students in Italy V1</i>
ID [ID type]	Not yet available [DOI]	
Chosen repository	AMSActa, institutional repository of Alma Mater Studiorum – University of Bologna, https://amsacta.unibo.it	
Version	1.0	
Team in charge	UNIBO	
Creator/s	Albanesi, Cinzia [UNIBO]	
Contributor/s	Cicognani, Elvira [UNIBO]; Prati, Gabriele [UNIBO]; Tzankova, Iana I. [UNIBO]; Compare, Christian [UNIBO]; Guarino, Antonella [UNIBO];	
Contact Person/s	Compare, Christian [UNIBO], christian.compare@unibo.it;	
Contents	<p>Data collected in schools in Italy through an anonymous survey. The dataset contains demographic data that are relevant in an intersectional perspective, e.g. migration background, SES, religion, political orientation, sexual orientation and identity, disability etc. These questions are crucial for the project as they represent important basis for understanding experiences of exclusion and marginalization based on categories of belonging or power unbalance.</p> <p>It also contains quantitative data regarding experiences of exclusion (e.g., Sternthal et al. scale, 2011), discrimination in examination contexts (e.g. school and community), social justice orientation (e.g. scale of Torres-Harding et al. 2012); participation experiences (cf. Enchikova et al. 2019) and quality of participation in schools, within organisations (Ferreira et al. 2012) and in deliberation processes (Nabatchi, 2007). Empowerment (Peterson et al., 2006; Speer et al., 2019), trust in institutions (Grootaert, 2004) and sense of belonging (Slaten et al., 2019). Data are collected using psychometrically validated scales.</p> <p>The data can be reused by researchers who want to compare it with similar data collected at other points in historical time as well as in other countries. Likewise, stakeholders may be interested in reanalyzing the data particularly with a focus on youth participation and deliberation in schools.</p>	
Data format	SPSS statistical data (.sav, .dat, .sps), Microsoft Excel (.xls/.xlsx), non-proprietary numerical tabular data (.csv)	
Data volume	5 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB	
Accessibility	Open access (CC BY 4.0)	
Related publication/s	Not yet available	

35	in progress	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T4.2.2 Survey of youth experience of intersectional exclusion and inclusion among organisation members in Italy V1</i>
ID [ID type]		Not yet available [DOI]
Chosen repository		AMSActa, institutional repository of Alma Mater Studiorum – University of Bologna, https://amsacta.unibo.it
Version		1.0
Team in charge		UNIBO
Creator/s		Albanesi, Cinzia [UNIBO]
Contributor/s		Cicognani, Elvira [UNIBO]; Prati, Gabriele [UNIBO]; Tzankova, Iana I. [UNIBO]; Compare, Christian [UNIBO]; Guarino, Antonella [UNIBO];
Contact Person/s		Compare, Christian [UNIBO], christian.compare@unibo.it;
Contents		<p>Data collected among members of youth organisations and groups in 6 EU countries (Denmark, Italy, Switzerland, the UK, Portugal and Finland) through anonymous survey. The dataset contains demographic data that are relevant in an intersectional perspective, e.g. migration background, SES, religion, political orientation, sexual orientation and identity, disability etc. These questions are crucial for the project as they represent important basis for understanding experiences of exclusion and marginalization based on categories of belonging or power unbalance. It also contains quantitative data regarding experiences of exclusion (e.g., Sternthal et al. scale, 2011), discrimination in examination contexts (e.g. school and community), social justice orientation (e.g. scale of Torres-Harding et al. 2012); participation experiences (cf. Enchikova et al. 2019) and quality of participation within organisations (Ferreira et al. 2012) and in deliberation processes (Nabatchi, 2007). Empowerment (Peterson et al., 2006; Speer et al., 2019), trust in institutions (Grootaert, 2004) and sense of belonging (Slaten et al., 2019). Data are collected using psychometrically validated scales.</p> <p>The data can be reused by researchers who want to compare it with similar data collected at other points in historical time as well as in other countries. Likewise, stakeholders may be interested in reanalyzing the data particularly with a focus on youth participation and deliberation in communities.</p>
Data format		SPSS statistical data (.sav, .dat, .sps), Microsoft Excel (.xls/.xlsx), non-proprietary numerical tabular data (.csv)
Data volume		5 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB
Accessibility		Open access (CC BY 4.0)
Related publication/s		Not yet available

36	in progress	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T4.2.2 Survey of youth experience of intersectional exclusion and inclusion among school students in Switzerland V1</i>
ID [ID type]		Not yet available [DOI]
Chosen repository		Zenodo, https://zenodo.org FORS Center, https://forscenter.ch/data-services/
Version		1.0
Team in charge		UNIGE
Creator/s		Giugni, Marco [UNIGE]
Contributor/s		Holecz, Valentina [UNIGE]; Stojanović, Nenad [UNIGE]
Contact Person/s		Giugni, Marco [UNIGE], marco.giugni@unige.ch ;
Contents		<p>Data collected in schools in Switzerland through an anonymous survey. The dataset contains demographic data that are relevant in an intersectional perspective, e.g. migration background, SES, religion, political orientation, sexual orientation and identity, disability etc. These questions are crucial for the project as they represent important basis for understanding experiences of exclusion and marginalization based on categories of belonging or power unbalance.</p> <p>It also contains quantitative data regarding experiences of exclusion (e.g., Sternthal et al. scale, 2011), discrimination in examination contexts (e.g. school and community), social justice orientation (e.g. scale of Torres-Harding et al. 2012); participation experiences (cf. Enchikova et al. 2019) and quality of participation in schools, within organisations (Ferreira et al. 2012) and in deliberation processes (Nabatchi, 2007). Empowerment (Peterson et al., 2006; Speer et al., 2019), trust in institutions (Grootaert, 2004) and sense of belonging (Slaten et al., 2019). Data are collected using psychometrically validated scales.</p> <p>The data can be reused by researchers who want to compare it with similar data collected at other points in historical time as well as in other countries. Likewise, stakeholders may be interested in reanalyzing the data particularly with a focus on youth participation and deliberation in schools.</p>
Data format		SPSS statistical data (.sav, .dat, .sps), Microsoft Excel (.xls/.xlsx), non-proprietary numerical tabular data (.csv)
Data volume		5 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB
Accessibility		Open access (CC BY 4.0)
Related publication/s		Not yet available

37	in progress	SINCRONY WP4 T4.2.2 Survey of youth experience of intersectional exclusion and inclusion among organisation members in Switzerland V1
ID [ID type]	Not yet available [DOI]	
Chosen repository	Zenodo, https://zenodo.org FORS Center, https://forscenter.ch/data-services/	
Version	1.0	
Team in charge	UNIGE	
Creator/s	Giugni, Marco [UNIGE]	
Contributor/s	Holecz, Valentina [UNIGE]; Stojanović, Nenad [UNIGE]	
Contact Person/s	Giugni, Marco [UNIGE], marco.giugni@unige.ch ;	
Contents	<p>Data collected among members of youth organisations and groups in Switzerland through anonymous survey. The dataset contains demographic data that are relevant in an intersectional perspective, e.g. migration background, SES, religion, political orientation, sexual orientation and identity, disability etc. These questions are crucial for the project as they represent important basis for understanding experiences of exclusion and marginalization based on categories of belonging or power unbalance.</p> <p>It also contains quantitative data regarding experiences of exclusion (e.g., Sternthal et al. scale, 2011), discrimination in examination contexts (e.g. school and community), social justice orientation (e.g, scale of Torres-Harding et al. 2012); participation experiences (cf. Enchikova et al. 2019) and quality of participation within organisations (Ferreira et al. 2012) and in deliberation processes (Nabatchi, 2007). Empowerment (Peterson et al., 2006; Speer et al., 2019), trust in institutions (Grootaert, 2004) and sense of belonging (Slaten et al., 2019). Data are collected using psychometrically validated scales.</p> <p>The data can be reused by researchers who want to compare it with similar data collected at other points in historical time as well as in other countries. Likewise, stakeholders may be interested in reanalyzing the data particularly with a focus on youth participation and deliberation in communities.</p>	
Data format	SPSS statistical data (.sav, .dat, .sps), Microsoft Excel (.xls/.xlsx), non-proprietary numerical tabular data (.csv)	
Data volume	5 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB	
Accessibility	Open access (CC BY 4.0)	
Related publication/s	Not yet available	

38	in progress	SINCRONY WP4 T4.2.2 Survey of youth experience of intersectional exclusion and inclusion among school students in the UK V1
ID [ID type]	Not yet available [DOI]	
Chosen repository	Figshare, https://figshare.com	
Version	1.0	
Team in charge	UNIMAN	
Creator/s	Pilkington, Hilary [UNIMAN];	
Contributor/s	Mirshak, Nadim [UNIMAN];	
Contact Person/s	Pilkington, Hilary [UNIMAN], hilary.pilkington@manchester.ac.uk ;	
Contents	<p>Data collected in schools in the UK through an anonymous survey. The dataset contains demographic data that are relevant in an intersectional perspective, e.g. migration background, SES, religion, political orientation, sexual orientation and identity, disability etc. These questions are crucial for the project as they represent important basis for understanding experiences of exclusion and marginalization based on categories of belonging or power unbalance.</p> <p>It also contains quantitative data regarding experiences of exclusion (e.g., Sternthal et al. scale, 2011), discrimination in examination contexts (e.g. school and community), social justice orientation (e.g. scale of Torres-Harding et al. 2012); participation experiences (cf. Enchikova et al. 2019) and quality of participation in schools, within organisations (Ferreira et al. 2012) and in deliberation processes (Nabatchi, 2007). Empowerment (Peterson et al., 2006; Speer et al., 2019), trust in institutions (Grootaert, 2004) and sense of belonging (Slaten et al., 2019). Data are collected using psychometrically validated scales.</p> <p>The data can be reused by researchers who want to compare it with similar data collected at other points in historical time as well as in other countries. Likewise, stakeholders may be interested in reanalyzing the data particularly with a focus on youth participation and deliberation in schools.</p>	
Data format	SPSS statistical data (.sav, .dat, .sps), Microsoft Excel (.xls/.xlsx), non-proprietary numerical tabular data (.csv)	
Data volume	5 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB	
Accessibility	Open access (CC BY 4.0)	
Related publication/s	Not yet available	

39	in progress	SINCRONY WP4 T4.2.2 Survey of youth experience of intersectional exclusion and inclusion among organisation members in the UK V1
ID [ID type]	Not yet available [DOI]	

39	in progress	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T4.2.2 Survey of youth experience of intersectional exclusion and inclusion among organisation members in the UK V1</i>
Chosen repository	Figshare, https://figshare.com	
Version	1.0	
Team in charge	UNIMAN	
Creator/s	Pilkington, Hilary [UNIMAN];	
Contributor/s	Mirshak, Nadim [UNIMAN];	
Contact Person/s	Pilkington, Hilary [UNIMAN], hilary.pilkington@manchester.ac.uk ;	
Contents	<p>Data collected among members of youth organisations and groups in 6 EU countries (Denmark, Italy, Switzerland, the UK, Portugal and Finland) through anonymous survey. The dataset contains demographic data that are relevant in an intersectional perspective, e.g. migration background, SES, religion, political orientation, sexual orientation and identity, disability etc. These questions are crucial for the project as they represent important basis for understanding experiences of exclusion and marginalization based on categories of belonging or power unbalance. It also contains quantitative data regarding experiences of exclusion (e.g., Sternthal et al. scale, 2011), discrimination in examination contexts (e.g. school and community), social justice orientation (e.g. scale of Torres-Harding et al. 2012); participation experiences (cf. Enchikova et al. 2019) and quality of participation within organisations (Ferreira et al. 2012) and in deliberation processes (Nabatchi, 2007). Empowerment (Peterson et al., 2006; Speer et al., 2019), trust in institutions (Grootaert, 2004) and sense of belonging (Slaten et al., 2019). Data are collected using psychometrically validated scales.</p> <p>The data can be reused by researchers who want to compare it with similar data collected at other points in historical time as well as in other countries. Likewise, stakeholders may be interested in reanalyzing the data particularly with a focus on youth participation and deliberation in communities.</p>	
Data format	SPSS statistical data (.sav, .dat, .sps), Microsoft Excel (.xls/.xlsx), non-proprietary numerical tabular data (.csv)	
Data volume	5 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB	
Accessibility	Open access (CC BY 4.0)	
Related publication/s	Not yet available	

40	in progress	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T4.2.2 Survey of youth experience of intersectional exclusion and inclusion among school students in Portugal V1</i>
ID [ID type]	Not yet available [DOI]	

40	in progress	SINCRONY WP4 T4.2.2 Survey of youth experience of intersectional exclusion and inclusion among school students in Portugal V1
Chosen repository		Zenodo, https://zenodo.org
Version		1.0
Team in charge		U.PORTO
Creator/s		Piedade, Filipe [U.PORTO];
Contributor/s		Menezes, Isabel [U.PORTO]; da Silva, Sofia Marques [U.PORTO]; Pais, Sofia Castanheira [U.PORTO]; Ferreira, Pedro [U.PORTO]; Ribeiro, Norberto [U.PORTO], Costa, Ana [U.PORTO], Piedade, Filipe [U.PORTO]
Contact Person/s		da Silva, Sofia Marques [U.PORTO]; sofiamsilva@fpce.up.pt ;
Contents		<p>Data collected in schools in Portugal through an anonymous survey. The dataset contains demographic data that are relevant in an intersectional perspective, e.g. migration background, SES, religion, political orientation, sexual orientation and identity, disability etc. These questions are crucial for the project as they represent important basis for understanding experiences of exclusion and marginalization based on categories of belonging or power unbalance.</p> <p>It also contains quantitative data regarding experiences of exclusion (e.g., Sternthal et al. scale, 2011), discrimination in examination contexts (e.g. school and community), social justice orientation (e.g. scale of Torres-Harding et al. 2012); participation experiences (cf. Enchikova et al. 2019) and quality of participation in schools, within organisations (Ferreira et al. 2012) and in deliberation processes (Nabatchi, 2007). Empowerment (Peterson et al., 2006; Speer et al., 2019), trust in institutions (Grootaert, 2004) and sense of belonging (Slaten et al., 2019). Data are collected using psychometrically validated scales.</p> <p>The data can be reused by researchers who want to compare it with similar data collected at other points in historical time as well as in other countries. Likewise, stakeholders may be interested in reanalyzing the data particularly with a focus on youth participation and deliberation in schools.</p>
Data format		SPSS statistical data (.sav, .dat, .sps), Microsoft Excel (.xls/.xlsx), non-proprietary numerical tabular data (.csv)
Data volume		5 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB
Accessibility		Open access (CC BY 4.0)
Related publication/s		Not yet available

41	in progress	SINCRONY WP4 T4.2.2 Survey of youth experience of intersectional exclusion and inclusion among organisation members in Portugal V1
ID [ID type]	Not yet available [DOI]	
Chosen repository	Zenodo, https://zenodo.org	
Version	1.0	
Team in charge	U.PORTO	
Creator/s	Piedade, Filipe [U.PORTO];	
Contributor/s	Menezes, Isabel [U.PORTO]; da Silva, Sofia Marques [U.PORTO]; Pais, Sofia Castanheira [U.PORTO]; Ferreira, Pedro [U.PORTO]; Ribeiro, Norberto [U.PORTO], Costa, Ana [U.PORTO], Piedade, Filipe [U.PORTO]	
Contact Person/s	da Silva, Sofia Marques [U.PORTO]; sofiamsilva@fpce.up.pt ;	
Contents	<p>Data collected among members of youth organisations and groups in Portugal through anonymous survey. The dataset contains demographic data that are relevant in an intersectional perspective, e.g. migration background, SES, religion, political orientation, sexual orientation and identity, disability etc. These questions are crucial for the project as they represent important basis for understanding experiences of exclusion and marginalization based on categories of belonging or power unbalance. It also contains quantitative data regarding experiences of exclusion (e.g., Sternthal et al. scale, 2011), discrimination in examination contexts (e.g. school and community), social justice orientation (e.g. scale of Torres-Harding et al. 2012); participation experiences (cf. Enchikova et al. 2019) and quality of participation within organisations (Ferreira et al. 2012) and in deliberation processes (Nabatchi, 2007). Empowerment (Peterson et al., 2006; Speer et al., 2019), trust in institutions (Grootaert, 2004) and sense of belonging (Slaten et al., 2019). Data are collected using psychometrically validated scales.</p> <p>The data can be reused by researchers who want to compare it with similar data collected at other points in historical time as well as in other countries. Likewise, stakeholders may be interested in reanalyzing the data particularly with a focus on youth participation and deliberation in communities.</p>	
Data format	SPSS statistical data (.sav, .dat, .sps), Microsoft Excel (.xls/.xlsx), non-proprietary numerical tabular data (.csv)	
Data volume	5 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB	
Accessibility	Open access (CC BY 4.0)	
Related publication/s	Not yet available	

42	in progress	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T4.2.2 Survey of youth experience of intersectional exclusion and inclusion among school students in Finland V1</i>
ID [ID type]		Not yet available [DOI]
Chosen repository		Zenodo, https://zenodo.org
Version		1.0
Team in charge		UTU
Creator/s		Korventausta, Miikka [UTU]
Contributor/s		Huttunen, Janette [UTU], Setälä, Maija [UTU], Leino, Mikko [UTU]
Contact Person/s		Korventausta, Miikka [UTU], miikka.korventausta@utu.fi ;
Contents		<p>Data collected in schools in Finland through an anonymous survey. The dataset contains demographic data that are relevant in an intersectional perspective, e.g. migration background, SES, religion, political orientation, sexual orientation and identity, disability etc. These questions are crucial for the project as they represent important basis for understanding experiences of exclusion and marginalization based on categories of belonging or power unbalance.</p> <p>It also contains quantitative data regarding experiences of exclusion (e.g., Sternthal et al. scale, 2011), discrimination in examination contexts (e.g. school and community), social justice orientation (e.g. scale of Torres-Harding et al. 2012); participation experiences (cf. Enchikova et al. 2019) and quality of participation in schools, within organisations (Ferreira et al. 2012) and in deliberation processes (Nabatchi, 2007). Empowerment (Peterson et al., 2006; Speer et al., 2019), trust in institutions (Grootaert, 2004) and sense of belonging (Slaten et al., 2019). Data are collected using psychometrically validated scales.</p> <p>The data can be reused by researchers who want to compare it with similar data collected at other points in historical time as well as in other countries. Likewise, stakeholders may be interested in reanalyzing the data particularly with a focus on youth participation and deliberation in schools.</p>
Data format		SPSS statistical data (.sav, .dat, .sps), Microsoft Excel (.xls/.xlsx), non-proprietary numerical tabular data (.csv)
Data volume		5 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB
Accessibility		Open access (CC BY 4.0)
Related publication/s		Not yet available

43	in progress	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T4.2.2 Survey of youth experience of intersectional exclusion and inclusion among organisation members in Finland V1</i>
ID [ID type]		Not yet available [DOI]

43	in progress	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T4.2.2 Survey of youth experience of intersectional exclusion and inclusion among organisation members in Finland V1</i>
Chosen repository		Zenodo, https://zenodo.org
Version		1.0
Team in charge		UTU
Creator/s		Korventausta, Miikka [UTU]
Contributor/s		Huttunen, Janette [UTU], Setälä, Maija [UTU], Leino, Mikko [UTU]
Contact Person/s		Korventausta, Miikka [UTU], miikka.korventausta@utu.fi ;
Contents		<p>Data collected among members of youth organisations and groups in 6 EU countries (Denmark, Italy, Switzerland, the UK, Portugal and Finland) through anonymous survey. The dataset contains demographic data that are relevant in an intersectional perspective, e.g. migration background, SES, religion, political orientation, sexual orientation and identity, disability etc. These questions are crucial for the project as they represent important basis for understanding experiences of exclusion and marginalization based on categories of belonging or power unbalance. It also contains quantitative data regarding experiences of exclusion (e.g., Sternthal et al. scale, 2011), discrimination in examination contexts (e.g. school and community), social justice orientation (e.g. scale of Torres-Harding et al. 2012); participation experiences (cf. Enchikova et al. 2019) and quality of participation within organisations (Ferreira et al. 2012) and in deliberation processes (Nabatchi, 2007). Empowerment (Peterson et al., 2006; Speer et al., 2019), trust in institutions (Grootaert, 2004) and sense of belonging (Slaten et al., 2019). Data are collected using psychometrically validated scales.</p> <p>The data can be reused by researchers who want to compare it with similar data collected at other points in historical time as well as in other countries. Likewise, stakeholders may be interested in reanalyzing the data particularly with a focus on youth participation and deliberation in communities.</p>
Data format		SPSS statistical data (.sav, .dat, .sps), Microsoft Excel (.xls/.xlsx), non-proprietary numerical tabular data (.csv)
Data volume		5 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB
Accessibility		Open access (CC BY 4.0)
Related publication/s		Not yet available

44	in progress	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T4.2.2 Cross-national survey of youth experience of intersectional exclusion and inclusion among school students V1</i>
ID [ID type]		Not yet available [DOI]

44	in progress	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T4.2.2 Cross-national survey of youth experience of intersectional exclusion and inclusion among school students V1</i>
Chosen repository	AMSActa, institutional repository of Alma Mater Studiorum – University of Bologna, https://amsacta.unibo.it	
Version	1.0	
Team in charge	UNIBO	
Creator/s	Albanesi, Cinzia [UNIBO]	
Contributor/s	Cicognani, Elvira [UNIBO]; Prati, Gabriele [UNIBO]; Tzankova, Iana I. [UNIBO]; Compare, Christian [UNIBO]; Guarino, Antonella [UNIBO]; Bruselius-Jensen, Maria [AAU]; Hansen da Cruz, Lika [AAU]; Dånge, Louise [AAU]; Giugni, Marco [UNIGE]; Holecz, Valentina [UNIGE]; Stojanović, Nenad [UNIGE]; Pilkington, Hilary [UNIMAN]; Mirshak, Nadim [UNIMAN]; Menezes, Isabel [U.PORTO]; da Silva, Sofia Marques [U.PORTO]; Pais, Sofia Castanheira [U.PORTO]; Ferreira, Pedro [U.PORTO]; Ribeiro, Norberto [U.PORTO], Costa, Ana [U.PORTO], Piedade, Filipe [U.PORTO]; Setälä, Maija [UTU]; Korventausta, Miikka [UTU]; Huttunen, Janette [UTU]; Leino, Mikko [UTU]	
Contact Person/s	Compare, Christian [UNIBO], christian.compare@unibo.it;	
Contents	<p>Data collected in schools in 6 EU countries (Denmark, Italy, Switzerland, the UK, Portugal and Finland) through an anonymous survey. The dataset contains demographic data that are relevant in an intersectional perspective, e.g. migration background, SES, religion, political orientation, sexual orientation and identity, disability etc. These questions are crucial for the project as they represent important basis for understanding experiences of exclusion and marginalization based on categories of belonging or power unbalance.</p> <p>It also contains quantitative data regarding experiences of exclusion (e.g., Sternthal et al. scale, 2011), discrimination in examination contexts (e.g. school and community), social justice orientation (e.g. scale of Torres-Harding et al. 2012); participation experiences (cf. Enchikova et al. 2019) and quality of participation in schools, within organisations (Ferreira et al. 2012) and in deliberation processes (Nabatchi, 2007). Empowerment (Peterson et al., 2006; Speer et al., 2019), trust in institutions (Grootaert, 2004) and sense of belonging (Slaten et al., 2019). Data are collected using psychometrically validated scales.</p> <p>The data can be reused by researchers who want to compare it with similar data collected at other points in historical time as well as in other countries. Likewise, stakeholders may be interested in reanalyzing the data particularly with a focus on youth participation and deliberation in schools.</p>	
Data format	SPSS statistical data (.sav, .dat, .sps), Microsoft Excel (.xls/.xlsx), non-proprietary numerical tabular data (.csv)	
Data volume	5 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB	
Accessibility	Open access (CC BY 4.0)	

44	in progress	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T4.2.2 Cross-national survey of youth experience of intersectional exclusion and inclusion among school students V1</i>
Related publication/s		Not yet available

45	in progress	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T4.2.2 Cross-national survey of youth experience of intersectional exclusion and inclusion among organisation members V1</i>
ID [ID type]		Not yet available [DOI]
Chosen repository		AMSActa, institutional repository of Alma Mater Studiorum – University of Bologna, https://amsacta.unibo.it
Version		1.0
Team in charge		UNIBO
Creator/s		Albanesi, Cinzia [UNIBO]
Contributor/s		Cicognani, Elvira [UNIBO]; Prati, Gabriele [UNIBO]; Tzankova, Iana I. [UNIBO]; Compare, Christian [UNIBO]; Guarino, Antonella [UNIBO]; Bruselius-Jensen, Maria [AAU]; Hansen da Cruz, Lika [AAU]; Dånge, Louise [AAU]; Giugni, Marco [UNIGE]; Holecz, Valentina [UNIGE]; Stojanović, Nenad [UNIGE]; Pilkington, Hilary [UNIMAN]; Mirshak, Nadim [UNIMAN]; Menezes, Isabel [U.PORTO]; da Silva, Sofia Marques [U.PORTO]; Pais, Sofia Castanheira [U.PORTO]; Ferreira, Pedro [U.PORTO]; Ribeiro, Norberto [U.PORTO]; Costa, Ana [U.PORTO]; Piedade, Filipe [U.PORTO]; Setälä, Maija [UTU]; Korventausta, Miikka [UTU]; Huttunen, Janette [UTU]; Leino, Mikko [UTU]
Contact Person/s		Compare, Christian [UNIBO], christian.compare@unibo.it;
Contents		Data collected among members of youth organisations and groups in 6 EU countries (Denmark, Italy, Switzerland, the UK, Portugal and Finland) through anonymous survey. The dataset contains demographic data that are relevant in an intersectional perspective, e.g. migration background, SES, religion, political orientation, sexual orientation and identity, disability etc. These questions are crucial for the project as they represent important basis for understanding experiences of exclusion and marginalization based on categories of belonging or power unbalance. It also contains quantitative data regarding experiences of exclusion (e.g., Sternthal et al. scale, 2011), discrimination in examination contexts (e.g. school and community), social justice orientation (e.g. scale of Torres-Harding et al. 2012); participation experiences (cf. Enchikova et al. 2019) and quality of participation within organisations (Ferreira et al. 2012) and in deliberation processes (Nabatchi, 2007). Empowerment (Peterson et al., 2006; Speer et al., 2019), trust in institutions (Grootaert, 2004) and sense of belonging (Slaten et al., 2019). Data are collected using psychometrically validated scales.

45	in progress	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T4.2.2 Cross-national survey of youth experience of intersectional exclusion and inclusion among organisation members V1</i>
		The data can be reused by researchers who want to compare it with similar data collected at other points in historical time as well as in other countries. Likewise, stakeholders may be interested in reanalyzing the data particularly with a focus on youth participation and deliberation in communities.
Data format	SPSS statistical data (.sav, .dat, .sps), Microsoft Excel (.xls/.xlsx), non-proprietary numerical tabular data (.csv)	
Data volume	5 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB	
Accessibility	Open access (CC BY 4.0)	
Related publication/s	Not yet available	

46	not yet available	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T4.2.3 Focus groups analysis of youth experience of intersectional exclusion and inclusion in Denmark V1</i>
ID [ID type]	Not available	
Chosen repository	DataDeposit, Aalborg University (controlled access repository)	
Version	1.0	
Team in charge	AAU	
Creator/s	Bruselius-Jensen, Maria [AAU];	
Contributor/s	Hansen da Cruz, Lika [AAU]; Dånge, Louise [AAU]	
Contact Person/s	Dånge, Louise [AAU], louseba@ikl.aau.dk;	
Contents	<p>The data consists of transcripts from 4 Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) with secondary school students and with youth from civic organizations/activist groups in Denmark, analyzed through thematic (Attride Stirling Thematic analysis) and conversational analysis. Socio-demographic data of the participants (age, educational level/working condition, place of living, gender, citizenship) is collected as information on the whole sample without pairing it with individual statements in the discussions.</p> <p>For ethical reasons, to protect the welfare of young FGD participants, the data will not be openly available. All data will be completely pseudonymized and stored safely at a secure in DataDeposit at Aalborg University which will not be open access. The drive will only be accessible to the project team members.</p> <p>The focus groups are aimed at studying prevailing narratives about youth, diversity, and participation, as well as counter-narratives and practices employed by young people, experiences of exclusion and intersectional inclusion, and the use of social media and digital tools to support engagement in deliberative processes.</p>	
Data format	MS Word (.docx), Plain Unicode text (.txt), OpenDocument text (.odt), Printable document (.pdf)	
Data volume	50 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB	
Accessibility	Closed access	
Related publication/s	Not yet available	

47	not yet available	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T4.2.3 Focus groups analysis of youth experience of intersectional exclusion and inclusion in Italy V1</i>
ID [ID type]	Not available	

47	not yet available	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T4.2.3 Focus groups analysis of youth experience of intersectional exclusion and inclusion in Italy V1</i>
Chosen repository	AMSActa, institutional repository of Alma Mater Studiorum – University of Bologna, https://amsacta.unibo.it	
Version	1.0	
Team in charge	UNIBO	
Creator/s	Albanesi, Cinzia [UNIBO]	
Contributor/s	Cicognani, Elvira [UNIBO]; Prati, Gabriele [UNIBO]; Tzankova, Iana I. [UNIBO]; Compare, Christian [UNIBO]; Guarino, Antonella [UNIBO];	
Contact Person/s	Albanesi, Cinzia [UNIBO], cinzia.albanesi@unibo.it ;	
Contents	<p>The data consists of transcripts from 4 Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) with secondary school students and with youth from civic organizations/activist groups in Italy, analyzed through thematic (Attride Stirling Thematic analysis) and conversational analysis. Socio-demographic data of the participants (age, educational level/working condition, place of living, gender, citizenship) is collected as information on the whole sample without pairing it with individual statements in the discussions.</p> <p>For ethical reasons, to protect the welfare of young FGD participants, the data will not be openly available. All data will be completely pseudonymized and stored safely at a secure encrypted drive at UNIBO. The drive will only be accessible to the project team members.</p> <p>The focus groups are aimed at studying prevailing narratives about youth, diversity, and participation, as well as counter-narratives and practices employed by young people, experiences of exclusion and intersectional inclusion, and the use of social media and digital tools to support engagement in deliberative processes.</p>	
Data format	MS Word (.docx), Plain Unicode text (.txt), OpenDocument text (.odt), Printable document (.pdf)	
Data volume	50 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB	
Accessibility	Closed access	
Related publication/s	Not yet available	

48	not yet available	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T4.2.3 Focus groups analysis of youth experience of intersectional exclusion and inclusion in Switzerland V1</i>
ID [ID type]	Not available	
Chosen repository	Controlled access repository	
Version	1.0	

48	not yet available	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T4.2.3 Focus groups analysis of youth experience of intersectional exclusion and inclusion in Switzerland V1</i>
Team in charge	UNIGE	
Creator/s	Giugni, Marco [UNIGE]	
Contributor/s	Holecz, Valentina [UNIGE]; Stojanović, Nenad [UNIGE]	
Contact Person/s	Giugni, Marco [UNIGE], marco.giugni@unige.ch;	
Contents	<p>The data consists of transcripts from 4 Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) with secondary school students and with youth from civic organizations/activist groups in Switzerland, analyzed through thematic (Attride Stirling Thematic analysis) and conversational analysis. Socio-demographic data of the participants (age, educational level/working condition, place of living, gender, citizenship) is collected as information on the whole sample without pairing it with individual statements in the discussions.</p> <p>For ethical reasons, to protect the welfare of young FGD participants, the data will not be openly available. All data will be completely pseudonymized and stored safely at a secure encrypted drive at UNIGE. The drive will only be accessible to the project team members.</p> <p>The focus groups are aimed at studying prevailing narratives about youth, diversity, and participation, as well as counter-narratives and practices employed by young people, experiences of exclusion and intersectional inclusion, and the use of social media and digital tools to support engagement in deliberative processes.</p>	
Data format	MS Word (.docx), Plain Unicode text (.txt), OpenDocument text (.odt), Printable document (.pdf)	
Data volume	50 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB	
Accessibility	Closed access	
Related publication/s	Not yet available	

49	not yet available	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T4.2.3 Focus groups analysis of youth experience of intersectional exclusion and inclusion in the UK V1</i>
ID [ID type]	Not available	
Chosen repository	Controlled access repository	
Version	1.0	
Team in charge	UNIMAN	
Creator/s	Pilkington, Hilary [UNIMAN];	

49	not yet available	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T4.2.3 Focus groups analysis of youth experience of intersectional exclusion and inclusion in the UK V1</i>
Contributor/s	Mirshak, Nadim [UNIMAN];	
Contact Person/s	Pilkington, Hilary [UNIMAN], hilary.pilkington@manchester.ac.uk;	
Contents	<p>The data consists of transcripts from 4 Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) with secondary school students and with youth from civic organizations/activist groups in the UK, analyzed through thematic (Attride Stirling Thematic analysis) and conversational analysis. Socio-demographic data of the participants (age, educational level/working condition, place of living, gender, citizenship) is collected as information on the whole sample without pairing it with individual statements in the discussions.</p> <p>For ethical reasons, to protect the welfare of young FGD participants, the data will not be openly available. All data will be completely pseudonymized and stored safely at a secure encrypted drive at UNIMAN. The drive will only be accessible to the project team members. The focus groups are aimed at studying prevailing narratives about youth, diversity, and participation, as well as counter-narratives and practices employed by young people, experiences of exclusion and intersectional inclusion, and the use of social media and digital tools to support engagement in deliberative processes.</p>	
Data format	MS Word (.docx), Plain Unicode text (.txt), OpenDocument text (.odt), Printable document (.pdf)	
Data volume	50 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB	
Accessibility	Closed access	
Related publication/s	Not yet available	

50	not yet available	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T4.2.3 Focus groups analysis of youth experience of intersectional exclusion and inclusion in Portugal V1</i>
ID [ID type]	Not available	
Chosen repository	Controlled access repository	
Version	1.0	
Team in charge	U.PORTO	
Creator/s	Piedade, Filipe [U.PORTO];	
Contributor/s	Menezes, Isabel [U.PORTO]; da Silva, Sofia Marques [U.PORTO]; Pais, Sofia Castanheira [U.PORTO]; Ferreira, Pedro [U.PORTO]; Ribeiro, Norberto [U.PORTO], Costa, Ana [U.PORTO], Piedade, Filipe [U.PORTO]	

50	not yet available	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T4.2.3 Focus groups analysis of youth experience of intersectional exclusion and inclusion in Portugal V1</i>
Contact Person/s	Menezes, Isabel [U.PORTO], imenezes@fpce.up.pt;	
Contents	<p>The data consists of transcripts from 4 Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) with secondary school students and with youth from civic organizations/activist groups in Portugal, analyzed through thematic (Attride Stirling Thematic analysis) and conversational analysis. Socio-demographic data of the participants (age, educational level/working condition, place of living, gender, citizenship) is collected as information on the whole sample without pairing it with individual statements in the discussions.</p> <p>For ethical reasons, to protect the welfare of young FGD participants, the data will not be openly available. All data will be completely pseudonymized and stored safely at a secure encrypted drive at U.PORTO. The drive will only be accessible to the project team members. The focus groups are aimed at studying prevailing narratives about youth, diversity, and participation, as well as counter-narratives and practices employed by young people, experiences of exclusion and intersectional inclusion, and the use of social media and digital tools to support engagement in deliberative processes.</p>	
Data format	MS Word (.docx), Plain Unicode text (.txt), OpenDocument text (.odt), Printable document (.pdf)	
Data volume	50 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB	
Accessibility	Closed access	
Related publication/s	Not yet available	

51	not yet available	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T4.2.3 Focus groups analysis of youth experience of intersectional exclusion and inclusion in Finland V1</i>
ID [ID type]	Not available	
Chosen repository	Seafire, institutional repository of University of Turku, seafire.utu.fi	
Version	1.0	
Team in charge	UTU	
Creator/s	Korventausta, Miikka [UTU]	
Contributor/s	Huttunen, Janette [UTU], Setälä, Maija [UTU], Leino, Mikko [UTU]	
Contact Person/s	Korventausta, Miikka [UTU], miikka.korventausta@utu.fi;	
Contents	The data consists of transcripts from 4 Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) with secondary school students and with youth from civic	

51	not yet available	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T4.2.3 Focus groups analysis of youth experience of intersectional exclusion and inclusion in Finland V1</i>
		<p>organizations/activist groups in Finland, analyzed through thematic (Attride Stirling Thematic analysis) and conversational analysis. Socio-demographic data of the participants (age, educational level/working condition, place of living, gender, citizenship) is collected as information on the whole sample without pairing it with individual statements in the discussions.</p> <p>For ethical reasons, to protect the welfare of young FGD participants, the data will not be openly available. All data will be completely pseudonymized and stored safely at a secure encrypted drive at UTU. The drive will only be accessible to the project team members.</p> <p>The focus groups are aimed at studying prevailing narratives about youth, diversity, and participation, as well as counter-narratives and practices employed by young people, experiences of exclusion and intersectional inclusion, and the use of social media and digital tools to support engagement in deliberative processes.</p>
Data format		MS Word (.docx), Plain Unicode text (.txt), OpenDocument text (.odt), Printable document (.pdf)
Data volume		50 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB
Accessibility		Closed access
Related publication/s		Not yet available

52	not yet available	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T4.2.3 Cross-national focus groups analysis of youth experience of intersectional exclusion and inclusion V1</i>
ID [ID type]		Not available
Chosen repository		DataDeposit, Aalborg University (controlled access repository)
Version		1.0
Team in charge		AAU
Creator/s		Bruselius-Jensen, Maria [AAU];
Contributor/s		Hansen da Cruz, Lika [AAU]; Dånge, Louise [AAU]; Albanesi, Cinzia [UNIBO]; Cicognani, Elvira [UNIBO]; Prati, Gabriele [UNIBO]; Tzankova, Iana I. [UNIBO]; Compare, Christian [UNIBO]; Guarino, Antonella [UNIBO]; Giugni, Marco [UNIGE]; Holecz, Valentina [UNIGE]; Stojanović, Nenad [UNIGE]; Pilkington, Hilary [UNIMAN]; Mirshak, Nadim [UNIMAN]; Menezes, Isabel [U.PORTO]; da Silva, Sofia Marques [U.PORTO]; Pais, Sofia Castanheira [U.PORTO]; Ferreira, Pedro [U.PORTO]; Ribeiro, Norberto [U.PORTO], Costa, Ana [U.PORTO], Piedade, Filipe [U.PORTO]; Setälä, Maija [UTU]; Korventausta, Miikka [UTU]; Huttunen, Janette [UTU]; Leino, Mikko [UTU]

52	not yet available	SINCRONY WP4 T4.2.3 Cross-national focus groups analysis of youth experience of intersectional exclusion and inclusion V1
Contact Person/s	Dånge, Louise [AAU], louseba@ikl.aau.dk;	
Contents	<p>The data consists of transcripts from Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) with secondary school students and with youth from civic organizations/activist groups in Denmark, Italy, Switzerland, the UK, Portugal and Finland, analyzed through thematic (Attride Stirling Thematic analysis) and conversational analysis. Socio-demographic data of the participants (age, educational level/working condition, place of living, gender, citizenship) is collected as information on the whole sample without pairing it with individual statements in the discussions.</p> <p>For ethical reasons, to protect the welfare of young FGD participants, the data will not be openly available. All data will be completely pseudonymized and stored safely at a secure in DataDeposit at Aalborg University, which will not be open access. The drive will only be accessible to the project team members</p> <p>The focus groups are aimed at studying prevailing narratives about youth, diversity, and participation, as well as counter-narratives and practices employed by young people, experiences of exclusion and intersectional inclusion, and the use of social media and digital tools to support engagement in deliberative processes.</p>	
Data format	MS Word (.docx), Plain Unicode text (.txt), OpenDocument text (.odt), Printable document (.pdf)	
Data volume	50 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB	
Accessibility	Closed access	
Related publication/s	Not yet available	

WP6 EVALUATION

WP6: This WP uses a mixed-method evaluation design to assess the quality, effectiveness, and impact of the two implementation pathways piloted in different countries and settings. Specifically, the WP will (O6.1) assess and monitor the perceived quality of the activities and the implementation process from the perspective of different stakeholders involved (process evaluation) to help the consortium identify challenges, strengths, and weaknesses in different contexts, addressing them in progress and adopting mitigation measures and strategies for adaptation that suit specific challenges/ contexts; (O6.2) adopt a pre-post evaluation design to assess the changes produced by the intervention on participants in each implementation pathway and type of setting (outcome evaluation), providing evidence of the efficacy of the I-DPP and I-PARD implementation pathways; (O6.3) use a qualitative design to evaluate the changes produced by the interventions in school and community settings in terms of influencing decision-makers and social actors (impact evaluation).

Lead: U.PORTO

Participants: AAU, ALDA, UIBK, UNIBO, UNIMAN, U.PORTO, UTU

Months: 16-38

Potential users for the datasets of this WP include researchers of the consortium, but also to researchers outside the consortium who may be interested in the approach adopted for evaluation, its sensitivity, its capacity to assess effectively the processes and the outcomes. Public servants, community organizations, and youth leaders may be interested in the evaluation tools developed by the project.

53	not yet available	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T6.1 Process and qualitative evaluation of SINCRONY implementations in Denmark V1</i>
ID [ID type]	Not yet available	
Chosen repository	Zenodo, https://zenodo.org	
Version	1.0	
Team in charge	AAU	
Creator/s	Bruselius-Jensen, Maria [AAU];	
Contributor/s	Hansen da Cruz, Lika [AAU]; Dånge, Louise [AAU]	
Contact Person/s	Dånge, Louise [AAU], louiseba@ikl.aau.dk ;	
Contents	This data set will include excerpts of the contents of interviews and focus groups discussions with Danish participants in the SINCRONY project	

53	not yet available	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T6.1 Process and qualitative evaluation of SINCRONY implementations in Denmark V1</i>
		implementations, used to evaluate the process and the impact of I-DPP and I-PARD. This data is used to assess and monitor the perceived quality of the activities and the implementation process of the SINCRONY intervention from the perspective of different stakeholders involved (process evaluation), as well as to assess the changes produced by the intervention on participants in each implementation pathway and type of setting (outcome evaluation).
Data format		MS Word (.docx), Plain Unicode text (.txt), OpenDocument text (.odt), Printable document (.pdf)
Data volume		50 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB
Accessibility		Excerpts: Open access (CC BY 4.0) Full data: Restricted access
Related publication/s		Not yet available

54	not yet available	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T6.1 Process and qualitative evaluation of SINCRONY implementations in Italy V1</i>
ID [ID type]		Not yet available
Chosen repository		AMSActa, institutional repository of Alma Mater Studiorum – University of Bologna, https://amsacta.unibo.it
Version		1.0
Team in charge		UNIBO
Creator/s		Albanesi, Cinzia [UNIBO]
Contributor/s		Cicognani, Elvira [UNIBO]; Prati, Gabriele [UNIBO]; Tzankova, Iana I. [UNIBO]; Compare, Christian [UNIBO]; Guarino, Antonella [UNIBO];
Contact Person/s		Albanesi, Cinzia [UNIBO], cinzia.albanesi@unibo.it ;
Contents		This data set will include excerpts of the contents of interviews and focus groups discussions with Italian participants in the SINCRONY project implementations, used to evaluate the process and the impact of I-DPP and I-PARD. This data is used to assess and monitor the perceived quality of the activities and the implementation process of the SINCRONY intervention from the perspective of different stakeholders involved (process evaluation), as well as to assess the changes produced by the intervention on participants in each implementation pathway and type of setting (outcome evaluation).

54	not yet available	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T6.1 Process and qualitative evaluation of SINCRONY implementations in Italy V1</i>
Data format	MS Word (.docx), Plain Unicode text (.txt), OpenDocument text (.odt), Printable document (.pdf)	
Data volume	50 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB	
Accessibility	Excerpts: Open access (CC BY 4.0) Full data: Restricted access	
Related publication/s	Not yet available	

55	not yet available	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T6.1 Process and qualitative evaluation of SINCRONY implementations in the UK V1</i>
ID [ID type]	Not yet available	
Chosen repository	Figshare, https://figshare.com	
Version	1.0	
Team in charge	UNIMAN	
Creator/s	Pilkington, Hilary [UNIMAN];	
Contributor/s	Mirshak, Nadim [UNIMAN];	
Contact Person/s	Pilkington, Hilary [UNIMAN], hilary.pilkington@manchester.ac.uk ;	
Contents	<p>This data set will include excerpts of the contents of interviews and focus groups discussions with UK participants in the SINCRONY project implementations, used to evaluate the process and the impact of I-DPP and I-PARD.</p> <p>This data is used to assess and monitor the perceived quality of the activities and the implementation process of the SINCRONY intervention from the perspective of different stakeholders involved (process evaluation), as well as to assess the changes produced by the intervention on participants in each implementation pathway and type of setting (outcome evaluation).</p>	
Data format	MS Word (.docx), Plain Unicode text (.txt), OpenDocument text (.odt), Printable document (.pdf)	
Data volume	50 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB	
Accessibility	Excerpts: Open access (CC BY 4.0) Full data: Restricted access	
Related publication/s	Not yet available	

56	not yet available	SINCRONY WP4 T6.1 Process and qualitative evaluation of SINCRONY implementations in Portugal V1
ID [ID type]	Not yet available	
Chosen repository	Zenodo, https://zenodo.org	
Version	1.0	
Team in charge	U.PORTO	
Creator/s	Piedade, Filipe [U.PORTO];	
Contributor/s	Menezes, Isabel [U.PORTO]; da Silva, Sofia Marques [U.PORTO]; Pais, Sofia Castanheira [U.PORTO]; Ferreira, Pedro [U.PORTO]; Ribeiro, Norberto [U.PORTO], Costa, Ana [U.PORTO], Piedade, Filipe [U.PORTO]	
Contact Person/s	Menezes, Isabel [U.PORTO], imenezes@fpce.up.pt ;	
Contents	<p>This data set will include excerpts of the contents of interviews and focus groups discussions with Portuguese participants in the SINCRONY project implementations, used to evaluate the process and the impact of I-DPP and I-PARD.</p> <p>This data is used to assess and monitor the perceived quality of the activities and the implementation process of the SINCRONY intervention from the perspective of different stakeholders involved (process evaluation), as well as to assess the changes produced by the intervention on participants in each implementation pathway and type of setting (outcome evaluation).</p>	
Data format	MS Word (.docx), Plain Unicode text (.txt), OpenDocument text (.odt), Printable document (.pdf)	
Data volume	50 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB	
Accessibility	Excerpts: Open access (CC BY 4.0) Full data: Restricted access	
Related publication/s	Not yet available	

57	not yet available	SINCRONY WP4 T6.1 Process and qualitative evaluation of SINCRONY implementations in Finland V1
ID [ID type]	Not yet available	
Chosen repository	Zenodo, https://zenodo.org	
Version	1.0	
Team in charge	UTU	

57	not yet available	SINCRONY WP4 T6.1 Process and qualitative evaluation of SINCRONY implementations in Finland V1
Creator/s	Korventausta, Miikka [UTU]	
Contributor/s	Setälä, Maija [UTU]; Janette Huttunen [UTU]; Leino, Mikko [UTU]	
Contact Person/s	Korventausta, Miikka [UTU], miikka.korventausta@utu.fi;	
Contents	<p>This data set will include excerpts of the contents of interviews and focus groups discussions with Portuguese participants in the SINCRONY project implementations, used to evaluate the process and the impact of I-DPP and I-PARD.</p> <p>This data is used to assess and monitor the perceived quality of the activities and the implementation process of the SINCRONY intervention from the perspective of different stakeholders involved (process evaluation), as well as to assess the changes produced by the intervention on participants in each implementation pathway and type of setting (outcome evaluation).</p>	
Data format	MS Word (.docx), Plain Unicode text (.txt), OpenDocument text (.odt), Printable document (.pdf)	
Data volume	50 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB	
Accessibility	Excerpts: Open access (CC BY 4.0) Full data: Restricted access	
Related publication/s	Not yet available	

58	not yet available	SINCRONY WP4 T6.1 Cross-national process and qualitative evaluation of SINCRONY implementations V1
ID [ID type]	Not yet available	
Chosen repository	Not yet available	
Version	1.0	
Team in charge	U.PORTO	
Creator/s	Piedade, Filipe [U.PORTO];	
Contributor/s	<p>Menezes, Isabel [U.PORTO], da Silva, Sofia Marques [U.PORTO]; Pais, Sofia Castanheira [U.PORTO]; Ferreira, Pedro [U.PORTO]; Ribeiro, Norberto [U.PORTO], Costa, Ana [U.PORTO], Piedade, Filipe [U.PORTO]; Bruselius-Jensen, Maria [AAU]; Hansen da Cruz, Lika [AAU]; Dånge, Louise [AAU]; Albanesi, Cinzia [UNIBO]; Cicognani, Elvira [UNIBO]; Prati, Gabriele [UNIBO]; Tzankova, Iana I. [UNIBO]; Compare, Christian [UNIBO]; Guarino, Antonella [UNIBO]; Pilkington, Hilary</p>	

58	not yet available	SINCRONY WP4 T6.1 Cross-national process and qualitative evaluation of SINCRONY implementations V1
		[UNIMAN]; Mirshak, Nadim [UNIMAN]; Setälä, Maija [UTU]; Korventausta, Miikka [UTU]; Huttunen, Janette [UTU]; Leino, Mikko [UTU]
Contact Person/s		Menezes, Isabel [U.PORTO], imenezes@fpce.up.pt;
Contents		<p>This data set will include excerpts of the contents of interviews and focus groups discussions with participants in the SINCRONY project implementations in Denmark, Italy, Switzerland, the UK, Portugal and Finland, used to evaluate the process and the impact of I-DPP and I-PARD.</p> <p>This data is used to assess and monitor the perceived quality of the activities and the implementation process of the SINCRONY intervention from the perspective of different stakeholders involved (process evaluation), as well as to assess the changes produced by the intervention on participants in each implementation pathway and type of setting (outcome evaluation).</p>
Data format		MS Word (.docx), Plain Unicode text (.txt), OpenDocument text (.odt), Printable document (.pdf)
Data volume		50 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB
Accessibility		Excerpts: Open access (CC BY 4.0) Full data: Restricted access
Related publication/s		Not yet available

59	not yet available	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T6.2 Quantitative pre-post evaluation of SINCRONY implementations in Denmark V1</i>
ID [ID type]	Not yet available [DOI]	
Chosen repository	Zenodo, https://zenodo.org	
Version	1.0	
Team in charge	AAU	
Creator/s	Bruselius-Jensen, Maria [AAU];	
Contributor/s	Hansen da Cruz, Lika [AAU]; Dånge, Louise [AAU]	
Contact Person/s	Dånge, Louise [AAU], louiseba@ikl.aau.dk ;	
Contents	<p>The data consists of quantitative survey data collected in the SINCRONY project implementations in Denmark before (T1: M21) and at the end (T2: M30) of the I-PARD pilot implementation, as well as six months later for a follow-up (T3: M36).</p> <p>This data is used to assess the changes produced by the intervention on participants (outcome evaluation). It will be anonymized during processing.</p>	
Data format	SPSS statistical data (.sav, .dat, .sps), Microsoft Excel (.xls/.xlsx), non-proprietary numerical tabular data (.csv)	
Data volume	5 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB	
Accessibility	Open access (CC BY 4.0)	
Related publication/s	Not yet available	

60	not yet available	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T6.2 Quantitative pre-post evaluation of SINCRONY implementations in Italy V1</i>
ID [ID type]	Not yet available [DOI]	
Chosen repository	AMSActa, institutional repository of Alma Mater Studiorum – University of Bologna, https://amsacta.unibo.it	
Version	1.0	
Team in charge	UNIBO	
Creator/s	Albanesi, Cinzia [UNIBO]	
Contributor/s	Cicognani, Elvira [UNIBO]; Prati, Gabriele [UNIBO]; Tzankova, Iana I. [UNIBO]; Compare, Christian [UNIBO]; Guarino, Antonella [UNIBO]	

60	not yet available	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T6.2 Quantitative pre-post evaluation of SINCRONY implementations in Italy V1</i>
Contact Person/s	Compare, Christian [UNIBO], christian.compare@unibo.it;	
Contents	The data consists of quantitative survey data collected in the SINCRONY project implementations in Italy before (T1: M21) and at the end (T2: M25 for I-DPP, M30 for I-PARD) of the pilot implementation, as well as six months later for a follow-up (T3: M31 for I-DPP, M36 for I-PARD). This data is used to assess the changes produced by the intervention on participants (outcome evaluation). It will be anonymized during processing.	
Data format	SPSS statistical data (.sav, .dat, .sps), Microsoft Excel (.xls/.xlsx), non-proprietary numerical tabular data (.csv)	
Data volume	5 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB	
Accessibility	Open access (CC BY 4.0)	
Related publication/s	Not yet available	

61	not yet available	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T6.2 Quantitative pre-post evaluation of SINCRONY implementations in the UK V1</i>
ID [ID type]	Not yet available [DOI]	
Chosen repository	Figshare, https://figshare.com	
Version	1.0	
Team in charge	UNIMAN	
Creator/s	Pilkington, Hilary [UNIMAN];	
Contributor/s	Mirshak, Nadim [UNIMAN];	
Contact Person/s	Pilkington, Hilary [UNIMAN], hilary.pilkington@manchester.ac.uk;	
Contents	The data consists of quantitative survey data collected in the SINCRONY project implementations in Denmark before (T1: M21) and at the end (T2: M30) of the I-PARD pilot implementation, as well as six months later for a follow-up (T3: M36). This data is used to assess the changes produced by the intervention on participants (outcome evaluation). It will be anonymized during processing.	
Data format	SPSS statistical data (.sav, .dat, .sps), Microsoft Excel (.xls/.xlsx), non-proprietary numerical tabular data (.csv)	
Data volume	5 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB	
Accessibility	Open access (CC BY 4.0)	

61	not yet available	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T6.2 Quantitative pre-post evaluation of SINCRONY implementations in the UK V1</i>
Related publication/s		Not yet available

62	not yet available	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T6.2 Quantitative pre-post evaluation of SINCRONY implementations in Portugal V1</i>
ID [ID type]		Not yet available [DOI]
Chosen repository		Zenodo, https://zenodo.org
Version		1.0
Team in charge		U.PORTO
Creator/s		Piedade, Filipe [U.PORTO];
Contributor/s		Menezes, Isabel [U.PORTO]; da Silva, Sofia Marques [U.PORTO]; Pais, Sofia Castanheira [U.PORTO]; Ferreira, Pedro [U.PORTO]; Ribeiro, Norberto [U.PORTO], Costa, Ana [U.PORTO], Piedade, Filipe [U.PORTO]
Contact Person/s		da Silva, Sofia Marques [U.PORTO]; sofiamsilva@fpce.up.pt ;
Contents		The data consists of quantitative survey data collected in the SINCRONY project implementations in Portugal before (T1: M21) and at the end (T2: M30) of the I-PARD pilot implementation, as well as six months later for a follow-up (T3: M36). This data is used to assess the changes produced by the intervention on participants (outcome evaluation). It will be anonymized during processing.
Data format		SPSS statistical data (.sav, .dat, .sps), Microsoft Excel (.xls/.xlsx), non-proprietary numerical tabular data (.csv)
Data volume		5 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB
Accessibility		Open access (CC BY 4.0)
Related publication/s		Not yet available

63	not yet available	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T6.2 Quantitative pre-post evaluation of SINCRONY implementations in Finland V1</i>
ID [ID type]		Not yet available [DOI]
Chosen repository		Zenodo, https://zenodo.org

63	not yet available	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T6.2 Quantitative pre-post evaluation of SINCRONY implementations in Finland V1</i>
Version		1.0
Team in charge		UTU
Creator/s		Korventausta, Miikka [UTU]
Contributor/s		Huttunen, Janette [UTU), Setälä, Maija [UTU], Leino, Mikko [UTU]
Contact Person/s		Korventausta, Miikka [UTU], miikka.korventausta@utu.fi;
Contents		The data consists of quantitative survey data collected in the SINCRONY project implementations in Finland before (T1: M21) and at the end (M25) of the I-DPP pilot implementation, as well as six months later for a follow-up (M31). This data is used to assess the changes produced by the intervention on participants in each implementation pathway and type of setting (outcome evaluation). It will be anonymized during processing.
Data format		SPSS statistical data (.sav, .dat, .sps), Microsoft Excel (.xls/.xlsx), non-proprietary numerical tabular data (.csv)
Data volume		5 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB
Accessibility		Open access (CC BY 4.0)
Related publication/s		Not yet available

64	not yet available	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T6.2 Cross-national quantitative pre-post evaluation of SINCRONY implementations V1</i>
ID [ID type]		Not yet available [DOI]
Chosen repository		AMSActa, institutional repository of Alma Mater Studiorum – University of Bologna, https://amsacta.unibo.it
Version		1.0
Team in charge		UNIBO
Creator/s		Albanesi, Cinzia [UNIBO]
Contributor/s		Cicognani, Elvira [UNIBO]; Prati, Gabriele [UNIBO]; Tzankova, Iana I. [UNIBO]; Compare, Christian [UNIBO]; Guarino, Antonella [UNIBO]; Bruselius-Jensen, Maria [AAU]; Hansen da Cruz, Lika [AAU]; Dånge, Louise [AAU]; Pilkington, Hilary [UNIMAN]; Mirshak, Nadim [UNIMAN]; Menezes, Isabel [U.PORTO]; da Silva, Sofia Marques [U.PORTO]; Pais, Sofia Castanheira [U.PORTO]; Ferreira, Pedro [U.PORTO]; Ribeiro, Norberto [U.PORTO], Costa, Ana [U.PORTO], Piedade, Filipe

64	not yet available	SINCRONY WP4 T6.2 Cross-national quantitative pre-post evaluation of SINCRONY implementations V1
		[U.PORTO]; Setälä, Maija [UTU]; Korventausta, Miikka [UTU]; Huttunen, Janette [UTU]; Leino, Mikko [UTU]
Contact Person/s		Compare, Christian [UNIBO], christian.compare@unibo.it;
Contents		The data consists of quantitative survey data collected in the SINCRONY project implementations in Denmark, Italy, Switzerland, the UK, Portugal and Finland before (T1: M21) and at the end (T2: M25 for I-DPP, M30 for I-PARD) of the pilot implementation, as well as six months later for a follow-up (T3: M31 for I-DPP, M36 for I-PARD). This data is used to assess the changes produced by the intervention on participants in each implementation pathway and type of setting (outcome evaluation). It will be anonymized during processing.
Data format		SPSS statistical data (.sav, .dat, .sps), Microsoft Excel (.xls/.xlsx), non-proprietary numerical tabular data (.csv)
Data volume		5 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB
Accessibility		Open access (CC BY 4.0)
Related publication/s		Not yet available

65	not yet available	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T6.3 Policy and community impact evaluation of SINCRONY implementations in Denmark V1</i>
ID [ID type]	Not yet available	
Chosen repository	Zenodo, https://zenodo.org	
Version	1.0	
Team in charge	AAU	
Creator/s	Bruselius-Jensen, Maria [AAU];	
Contributor/s	Hansen da Cruz, Lika [AAU]; Dånge, Louise [AAU]	
Contact Person/s	Dånge, Louise [AAU], louiseba@ikl.aau.dk ;	
Contents	This data set will include excerpts of the contents of interviews with Danish national and local policymakers, community leaders (representatives of NGOs, local projects, services and institutions, school decision-makers and staff, and youth groups, about the impact of the SINCRONY implementations in respective communities.	
Data format	MS Word (.docx), Plain Unicode text (.txt), OpenDocument text (.odt), Printable document (.pdf)	
Data volume	50 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB	
Accessibility	Excerpts: Open access (CC BY 4.0) Full data: Restricted access	
Related publication/s	Not yet available	

66	not yet available	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T6.3 Policy and community impact evaluation of SINCRONY implementations in Italy V1</i>
ID [ID type]	Not yet available	
Chosen repository	AMSActa, institutional repository of Alma Mater Studiorum – University of Bologna, https://amsacta.unibo.it	
Version	1.0	
Team in charge	UNIBO	
Creator/s	Albanesi, Cinzia [UNIBO]	
Contributor/s	Cicognani, Elvira [UNIBO]; Prati, Gabriele [UNIBO]; Tzankova, Iana I. [UNIBO]; Compare, Christian [UNIBO]; Guarino, Antonella [UNIBO];	

66	not yet available	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T6.3 Policy and community impact evaluation of SINCRONY implementations in Italy V1</i>
Contact Person/s	Albanesi, Cinzia [UNIBO], cinzia.albanesi@unibo.it;	
Contents	This data set will include excerpts of the contents of interviews with Italian national and local policymakers, community leaders (representatives of NGOs, local projects, services and institutions, school decision-makers and staff, and youth groups, about the impact of the SINCRONY implementations in respective communities.	
Data format	MS Word (.docx), Plain Unicode text (.txt), OpenDocument text (.odt), Printable document (.pdf)	
Data volume	50 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB	
Accessibility	Excerpts: Open access (CC BY 4.0) Full data: Restricted access	
Related publication/s	Not yet available	

67	not yet available	<i>SINCRONY WP4 T6.3 Policy and community impact evaluation of SINCRONY implementations in the UK V1</i>
ID [ID type]	Not yet available	
Chosen repository	Figshare, https://figshare.com	
Version	1.0	
Team in charge	UNIMAN	
Creator/s	Pilkington, Hilary [UNIMAN];	
Contributor/s	Mirshak, Nadim [UNIMAN];	
Contact Person/s	Pilkington, Hilary [UNIMAN], hilary.pilkington@manchester.ac.uk;	
Contents	This data set will include excerpts of the contents of interviews with UK national and local policymakers, community leaders (representatives of NGOs, local projects, services and institutions, school decision-makers and staff, and youth groups, about the impact of the SINCRONY implementations in respective communities.	
Data format	MS Word (.docx), Plain Unicode text (.txt), OpenDocument text (.odt), Printable document (.pdf)	
Data volume	50 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB	
Accessibility	Excerpts: Open access (CC BY 4.0) Full data: Restricted access	

67	not yet available	SINCRONY WP4 T6.3 Policy and community impact evaluation of SINCRONY implementations in the UK V1
Related publication/s		Not yet available

68	not yet available	SINCRONY WP4 T6.3 Policy and community impact evaluation of SINCRONY implementations in Portugal V1
ID [ID type]		Not yet available
Chosen repository		Zenodo, https://zenodo.org
Version		1.0
Team in charge		U.PORTO
Creator/s		Piedade, Filipe [U.PORTO];
Contributor/s		Menezes, Isabel [U.PORTO]; da Silva, Sofia Marques [U.PORTO]; Pais, Sofia Castanheira [U.PORTO]; Ferreira, Pedro [U.PORTO]; Ribeiro, Norberto [U.PORTO], Costa, Ana [U.PORTO], Piedade, Filipe [U.PORTO]
Contact Person/s		Menezes, Isabel [U.PORTO], imenezes@fpce.up.pt ;
Contents		This data set will include excerpts of the contents of interviews with Portuguese national and local policymakers, community leaders (representatives of NGOs, local projects, services and institutions, school decision-makers and staff, and youth groups, about the impact of the SINCRONY implementations in respective communities.
Data format		MS Word (.docx), Plain Unicode text (.txt), OpenDocument text (.odt), Printable document (.pdf)
Data volume		50 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB
Accessibility		Excerpts: Open access (CC BY 4.0) Full data: Restricted access
Related publication/s		Not yet available

69	not yet available	SINCRONY WP4 T6.3 Policy and community impact evaluation of SINCRONY implementations in Finland V1
ID [ID type]		Not yet available
Chosen repository		Zenodo, https://zenodo.org
Version		1.0

69	not yet available	SINCRONY WP4 T6.3 Policy and community impact evaluation of SINCRONY implementations in Finland V1
Team in charge	UTU	
Creator/s	Korventausta, Miikka [UTU]	
Contributor/s	Setälä, Maija [UTU]; Janette Huttunen [UTU]; Leino, Mikko [UTU]	
Contact Person/s	Korventausta, Miikka [UTU], miikka.korventausta@utu.fi;	
Contents	This data set will include excerpts of the contents of interviews with Finnish national and local policymakers, community leaders (representatives of NGOs, local projects, services and institutions, school decision-makers and staff, and youth groups, about the impact of the SINCRONY implementations in respective communities.	
Data format	MS Word (.docx), Plain Unicode text (.txt), OpenDocument text (.odt), Printable document (.pdf)	
Data volume	50 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB	
Accessibility	Excerpts: Open access (CC BY 4.0) Full data: Restricted access	
Related publication/s	Not yet available	

70	not yet available	SINCRONY WP4 T6.3 Cross-national policy and community impact evaluation of SINCRONY implementations V1
ID [ID type]	Not yet available	
Chosen repository	Zenodo, https://zenodo.org	
Version	1.0	
Team in charge	U.PORTO	
Creator/s	Piedade, Filipe [U.PORTO];	
Contributor/s	Menezes, Isabel [U.PORTO], da Silva, Sofia Marques [U.PORTO]; Pais, Sofia Castanheira [U.PORTO]; Ferreira, Pedro [U.PORTO]; Ribeiro, Norberto [U.PORTO], Costa, Ana [U.PORTO], Piedade, Filipe [U.PORTO]; Bruselius-Jensen, Maria [AAU]; Hansen da Cruz, Lika [AAU]; Dånge, Louise [AAU]; Albanesi, Cinzia [UNIBO]; Cicognani, Elvira [UNIBO]; Prati, Gabriele [UNIBO]; Tzankova, Iana I. [UNIBO]; Compare, Christian [UNIBO]; Guarino, Antonella [UNIBO]; Pilkington, Hilary [UNIMAN]; Mirshak, Nadim [UNIMAN]; Setälä, Maija [UTU]; Korventausta, Miikka [UTU]; Huttunen, Janette [UTU]; Leino, Mikko [UTU]	

70	not yet available	SINCRONY WP4 T6.3 Cross-national policy and community impact evaluation of SINCRONY implementations V1
Contact Person/s	Menezes, Isabel [U.PORTO], imenezes@fpce.up.pt;	
Contents	This data set will include excerpts of the contents of interviews with national and local policymakers, community leaders (representatives of NGOs, local projects, services and institutions, school decision-makers and staff, and youth groups, about the impact of the SINCRONY implementations in respective communities in Denmark, Italy, Switzerland, the UK, Portugal and Finland.	
Data format	MS Word (.docx), Plain Unicode text (.txt), OpenDocument text (.odt), Printable document (.pdf)	
Data volume	50 MB, the size of data does not exceed 1GB	
Accessibility	Excerpts: Open access (CC BY 4.0) Full data: Restricted access	
Related publication/s	Not yet available	

Annex II: Open Access status of project publications

The following table (Table 9) will be employed in further versions of the document to report the updated list describing the open access status of the project publications and the underlying datasets.

Table 9. *Publications and related datasets*

Publications	
Bibliographic citation of the publication	
Link to copy archived in repository	
Related dataset/s	
Bibliographic citation of the publication	
Link to copy archived in repository	
Related dataset/s	
Bibliographic citation of the publication	
Link to copy archived in repository	
Related dataset/s	
Bibliographic citation of the publication	
Link to copy archived in repository	
Related dataset/s	
[...]	

Annex III: “README” file template

A “README” file is a document that will be deposited with each dataset, containing relevant information about dataset authorship, terms of reuse and responsibilities, explaining dataset content and structure, collection procedures and analysis (such as file specifics, methodologies, codebooks of variables, data sources, and further necessary notes). The template of the README file that will be used by SINCRONY is shown here.

README file

Dataset Title: “[insert title as defined in the DMP]”

Dataset Author/s: **Name Surname** (Affiliation), ORCID (if available);

[Add one or more creators, if present]

Dataset Contributor/s: **Name Surname** (Affiliation), ORCID (if available);

[Add one or more contributors, if present. Otherwise, cancel this line]

Dataset Contact Person/s: **Name Surname** (Affiliation), ORCID (if available), email;

[Add one or more contact person]

Dataset License: this dataset is distributed under a **(INSERT LICENSE)**

[Insert the chosen license as indicated in the DMP: e.g. “this dataset is distributed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) license, <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>”]

Publication Year: **(insert YEAR)**

Project Info: **[insert PROJECT ACRONYM]** (**[project full title]**), funded by European Union, Horizon 2020 Programme. Grant Agreement num. **[insert grant agreement number]**; **[insert project website url]**

Dataset Contents

The dataset consists of:

[Indicate the files that compose the dataset and their name and format.

WE STRONGLY SUGGEST YOU TO FOLLOW THE EXAMPLES PROVIDED FOR THE FILE NAMING, MATCHING THE DATASET FILENAME WITH THE README ONE

In the following examples the datasets were composed by only one file. In case the dataset consists of more files you can name them as described and put them in a compressed folder. In this case readme file name should match the compressed folder name]

EXAMPLE1

- 1 textual qualitative file saved in .rtf format

“**ProjectAcronym_WP3_T3-2_ItalyInterviews_20161221_v01.rtf**”

[structure of the filename “ProjectAcronym_insert WP number_insert Task number, e.g. T3.2_ insert Content Describing Keywords_insert date YYYYMMDD_insert version, if needed.format”]

Suggested format:

-for textual qualitative data .rtf or .txt

-for tabular quantitative and qualitative data .csv

avoid proprietary formats such as .doc/.docx and .xls/.xlsx]

- 1 README file

“**README_ProjectAcronym_WP3_T3-2_ItalyInterviews_20161221_v01.rtf**”

[Same naming as the dataset file. Preferred format .rtf/.txt, allowed format .pdf]

EXAMPLE2

- 1 tabular quantitative file saved in .csv format
“ProjectAcronym_WP7_T7.3_Questionnaire_Sweden_20170905.csv”
- 1 README file
“README_ProjectAcronym_WP7_T7-3_Questionnaire_Sweden_20170905.rtf”

Dataset Documentation

Abstract

[Insert a brief abstract describing the content of the dataset]

Content of the files:

- file [Insert filename] contains ...

[Provide a brief description of the content of the file/s. This is an example of how you could start]

- file [Insert filename] contains ...

File specifics

[Provide useful info regarding file conversion etc... (Optional)]

Please indicate instruction/technical info in order to allow potential users to correctly visualize and reuse your data (e.g. specific software, ...).

In case of data converted in open formats it could be useful to provide some further information. For example if you deposit for long term preservation a .csv file derived from an excel you can describe the conversion. Here is an example of description of conversion using libre office calc software:

To create the .csv files, “LibreOffice Calc” version: 5.1.4.2 (portable) was used, with the following specifics:

- Character set *Europa occidentale (Windows-1252/WinLatin1)*
- Field delimiter « , » (*comma*)
- Text delimiter « ” » (*quotes*)

Notes

[Related to the whole dataset or to single files of a multi-file dataset (Optional)]

Data sources

[Optional]

Methodologies

[If necessary to understand how to reuse data]

Codebook of variables

[If necessary to understand the meaning of the variables]

Instructions, examples and footnotes in should be deleted from final version.